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**Lebenszyklusanalyse (Ökobilanzierung) naturnaher Verfahren
zur Behandlung von Niederschlagswasser in urbanen
Räumen**

**Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of Nature Based
Treatment Technologies for Rainwater Treatment
in Urban Areas**

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Note (10/2025): The LCA calculations related to the Urban Rainshell (URS, Case Study 4b) are blackened in this Master Thesis as they were based on input data from the supplier derived with a non-compatible method to the one used in this master thesis. The calculations were therefore updated for the URS accordingly and are supplied in Deliverable 3.7 "Carbon Footprint and Cost Index for All seven treatment Technologies in StopUP"

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Masterarbeit

von

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Abstract

The present thesis is framed within the activities envisioned in the StopUP project of the European Union (EU), aimed at researching, designing, and validating innovative technical solutions for pollutant retention. Within the research task, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is integrated to provide information to developers and researchers on the environmental implications associated with materials and energy use over the lifespan of each technology. The case studies analyzed are classified into three groups according to their function in urban water management. The first group focuses on preventing the wet weather flows from contributing to Combined Sewer Overflows (CSO) through pretreatment. This category addresses average concentration and includes a retention soil filter in an as-built and compact design, a Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) smart management, and an improved constructed wetland. The second group also involves CSO management technology; however, the filtration-adsorption system is used for peak concentration. The third comprises runoff management systems, targeting stormwater treatment at its source. This group includes a sand filter, a shell filter, and a bioretention cell. The case studies were compared to three baseline scenarios: no intervention, WWTP operation, and a storage tank with subsequent treatment. Seven midpoint environmental indicators were quantified for each system in the construction and operation phases. Impacts have been classified into point source-related and infrastructure-related. Point source emissions are associated with water eutrophication and ecotoxicity. In these indicators, the technologies showed a substantial improvement in water quality compared to the no-intervention scenario. However, incorporating construction and operation generates a trade-off in other impact categories, namely climate change, acidification, and water consumption, resulting in infrastructure-related impacts. Within the scenarios evaluated WWTP shows the lowest environmental impact in all indicators, as only its operation is considered, and it also achieves the highest treatment efficiency thanks to its advanced processes. In CSO management, the retention soil filter has the second lowest infrastructure-related impact, followed by the concrete storage unit. The compact variant exhibits high impacts under current development conditions due to its bioflocculant consumption during operation, accounting for 55% of its total footprint in climate change. As defined within the system boundaries, the improved constructed wetland presented the highest burdens. However, its performance improves when handling less polluted water. The filtration-adsorption system has a seven times higher impact than the storage tank. In terms of runoff management, the systems provide a preferable solution to the storage tank, reducing GWP by 95% with the BRC, 80% with the sand filter, and 63% with the shell filter, mainly due to less use of concrete and metals, the systems show a more significant impact from material transport than from material production itself.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation	Unit
ATD	Ingenieurgesellschaft für Abwasserwirtschaft und technische Dienstleistungen (ger.): Engineering company for wastewater management and technical services	
BOD ₅	Biological Oxygen Demand	[mg/L]
BRC	Bioretention Cell	
CaCO ₃	Calcium Carbonate	
COD	Chemical Oxygen Demand	[mg/L]
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide	
CS	Case Study	
CSO	Combined Sewer Overflow	
CW	Constructed Wetland	
DN	Nominal Diameter	
DWA	Deutsche Vereinigung für Wasserwirtschaft, Abwasser und Abfall e.V. (ger.): German Association for Water, Wastewater and Waste	
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency	
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration	
EQS	Environmental Quality Standards	
EU	European Union	
FEP	Freshwater Eutrophication Potential	[kg P-Eq]
FETP	Freshwater Ecotoxicity Potential	[kg 1.4-DCB-Eq]
FU	Functional Unit	
GHG	Greenhouse Gas	
GWP	Global Warming Potential	[kg CO ₂ -Eq]
HDPE	High-Density Polyethylene	
HFCW	Horizontal Flow Constructed Wetland	
HRT	Hydraulic Retention Time	
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment	
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory	
LID	Low Impact Development	
FHNW	University of Applied Sciences Northwestern Switzerland	
ISSBAT	Higher Institute of Applied Biological Sciences of Tunis	

MEP	Marine Eutrophication Potential	[kg N-Eq]
METP	Marine Ecotoxicity Potential	[kg 1.4-DCB-Eq]
N	Nitrogen	
NBS	Nature-Based Solution	
NaCl	Sodium Chloride	
NaOH	Sodium Hydroxide	
Na ₂ CO ₃	Sodium Carbonate	
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	
P	Phosphorus	
PAHs	Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons	
PE	Population Equivalent	
PP	Polypropylene	
PSE	Point Source Emission	
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride	
RSF	Retention Soil Filter	
RTC	Real-Time Control	
RWTH	Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule	
SBR	Sequential Batch Reactor	
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal	
SuDS	Sustainable Drainage System	
TAP	Terrestrial Acidification Potential	[kg SO ₂ -Eq]
TN	Total Nitrogen	
TP	Total Phosphorus	
TSS	Total Suspended Solids	
TVS	Total Volatile Solids	
UN	United Nations	
UNIBO	University of Bologna	
URS	Urban Rain Shell	
VFCW	Vertical Flow Constructed Wetland	
WCP	Water Consumption Potential	[m ³]
WWTP	Waste Water Treatment Plant	

1 Introduction

By 2050, at least a quarter of the world population is expected to live in countries with severe freshwater stress (UN, 2018). Contributing factors such as climate change, urbanization, and population growth further increase the pressure on the environment, compromising the sustainability of water resources (KOURTIS and TSIHRINTZIS, 2021). Thus, the water cycle is disrupted. Climate change affects precipitation patterns (DYRRDAL et al., 2021). Urbanization proliferates the impervious footprint, reducing natural hydrologic flow pathways and impeding groundwater recharge (COOK, 2007). Moreover, population expansion increases pollutant loads discharged to the aquatic environment (BECOUBE-LAREURE et al., 2019). All this, together with the aged sewage infrastructures, results in more frequent overflows, discharging large volumes of untreated water, and flooding (KOURTIS and TSIHRINTZIS, 2021).

Although there are several European directives on wastewater treatment (91/271/EEC), bathing water (2006/7/EC), and general water quality (2000/60/EC), water bodies remain threatened by point and diffuse source pollution (PERRY et al., 2024). For instance, despite the progress made with the Water Framework Directive, which aims to achieve good ecological and chemical status of water bodies, Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs) remain one of the leading causes of the failure to achieve adequate water quality (RIZZO et al., 2020).

Overflows from the combined sewer and stormwater network trigger the transport of pollutants, including suspended solids, nutrients, heavy metals, and pathogens (RASHID et al., 2023; SHRESTHA et al., 2018). The impacts are diverse and can occur in the short or long term. These include oxygen depletion due to increased biodegradation from high loads of organic matter and ammonium, bacteria, and viruses can cause hygienic pollution, nutrients lead to eutrophication, and heavy metals can accumulate in organisms and sediments (GAMERITH, 2011). In addition to impacts on freshwater ecosystems, human health and local recreation can also be affected, with economic and social repercussions (PERRY et al., 2024). The costs of the required measures are significant, so the interest in a detailed understanding of the processes is evident (GAMERITH, 2011).

Diverse measures are being developed to address the adverse effects of pollutants in water. In the European Union, for instance, the StopUP project has been established. Under this initiative, several case studies are being conducted to develop and test contaminant retention technologies. Solutions include CSO treatment systems, such as a compact retention soil filter, a filtration-adsorption system, the smart management of a Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP), and an improved constructed wetland, as well as runoff management systems, such as a sand filter, a shell filter, and a bioretention cell. The present work addresses these technologies, investigating the associated environmental footprint.

1.1 Stormwater management in urban water systems

Runoff is generated during rainfall events and, depending on the degree of urbanization and pollution, can either drain into the ground for treatment by infiltration or be conveyed through canalization. In combined sewer systems, however, only a certain amount of the total runoff can be hydraulically channeled and treated by WWTPs. The remaining volume is usually stored temporarily or, in case capacity is exceeded, released out of the system into receiving water bodies through CSO structures (GAMERITH, 2011). This option represents the most conventional method of wet weather flow management (PIRO et al., 2010).

In addition to storage, technologies such as retention soil filters or constructed wetlands can alleviate the impact related to CSO discharges. Further solutions have emerged to counteract the volume conveyed into channels and move from the “end-of-pipe” approach to stormwater management immediately after its generation, facilitating adaptation to the natural water cycle. In this regard, Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS) have been developed, maximizing infiltration into the ground and the use of ecotechnologies such as bioretention filters, rain gardens, and wetlands to buffer and treat flows (TONDERA et al., 2018). Furthermore, these systems have a nature-based approach, implying that natural treatment processes are mimicked, with low energy and chemical consumption (BOANO et al., 2020).

Adopting stormwater technologies introduces construction and operating costs, as well as an environmental footprint, and may generate, for instance, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Therefore, solutions must be innovative regarding efficiency and sustainability performance. (BRUNHOFFEROVA et al., 2024)

1.2 Sustainability in stormwater management

Addressing runoff and sewer overflows through stormwater management should contribute overall to sustainable development, specifically by supporting the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (United Nations), particularly SDG No. 6, “safe drinking water and sanitation”; No. 11, “sustainable cities and communities”; No. 13, “climate action”; and No. 14, “life below water.”

Stormwater treatment technologies are often installed regardless of the environmental impacts of their materials, construction, transportation, operation, and maintenance (O’SULLIVAN et al., 2015). A more assertive decision should be based on both technical and environmental studies. In this context, methodologies for quantifying impacts should be used. Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) is one of them, allowing the identification of the most important impact categories within the system, wherein the system these impacts are created, and what their sources are (SLAGSTAD and BRATTEBØ, 2014).

Currently, environmental assessment employing life cycle assessment is considered a useful analytical tool for developing metrics to compare and evaluate processes and products in relation to their potential environmental impacts (HAUSCHILD et al., 2013). For instance, studies by O'SULLIVAN et al. (2015) determined, through a comparative LCA study between different technologies, that the concrete-based treatment systems had the highest environmental impacts, while infiltrative raingardens showed the lowest overall. BHATT et al. (2019) compared various low-impact development (LID) technologies versus a traditional pipe and pond infrastructure, revealing that LID impacts are 20% lower compared to detention ponds.

1.3 Research objectives

The present study is framed within the activities envisioned in the StopUP project of the European Union (EU), aimed at researching, designing, and validating innovative technical solutions for pollutant retention. Within the research task, LCA is integrated to provide information to developers and researchers on the environmental implications associated with materials and energy use over the lifespan of each technology.

The specific aims are:

- To provide an inventory of the construction and operation phases for each stormwater management technology, with specification of system boundaries and corresponding assumptions.
- To assess the environmental impacts of the systems in the construction and operation stages using LCA, for the impact categories of climate change, acidification, eutrophication, ecotoxicity and water use.
- To compare the results of each system with reference scenarios, including no intervention, treatment at the WWTP, and storage tank retention followed by treatment at the WWTP.
- To create a framework to allow comparison between technologies and subsequent ranking.

1.4 Structure of the thesis

An overview of the case studies is presented in Chapter 2 of this thesis, followed by a brief review of the environmental burdens of the materials used in the construction and operation of the technologies. Chapter 3 describes the methodology, presenting the standardization of the input parameters to facilitate comparability between the case studies. It also introduces the LCA approach, setting out the system boundaries and key assumptions. Chapter 4 presents the results and highlights the factors contributing most to the environmental impact. Chapter 5 discusses the findings and incorporates a sensitivity analysis. Finally, Chapter 6 presents the conclusions and considerations for future research.

2 Stormwater treatment technologies and materials sustainability

The stormwater treatment technologies considered in this study are presented below, providing a technical and structural overview. In addition, a brief section is included focusing on the impacts associated with the materials and services used during the life cycle of these technologies.

2.1 Introduction to the case studies

2.1.1 Combined sewer overflow systems

Combined sewer systems are constructed to carry both dry weather flow that includes domestic wastewater, industrial discharges, groundwater infiltration, and stormwater runoff from precipitation (QUARANTA et al., 2022a). Under normal operation, these systems transport the collected flow to a wastewater treatment plant (WWTP). However, when the flow exceeds the capacity of the system, Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs) discharge untreated water directly into receiving water bodies, representing a potential source of pollution (ATAUZZAMAN and ALI, 2022).

According to PASSERAT et al. (2011), CSOs impact aquatic ecosystems depending on the types of pollutants and their temporal and spatial dynamics. The main effects include depletion of dissolved oxygen through biodegradation of organic matter, increased turbidity, which limits photosynthesis, the presence of organic micropollutants and heavy metals, and high concentrations of pathogenic microorganisms and fecal indicators. Studies conducted by VIVIANO et al. (2017) show the magnitude of these impacts. According to the research, CSO discharges are responsible for about 50 % of the total phosphorus load in the Lambro River in northern Italy.

Several mitigation strategies have been developed in response to the negative impact of uncontrolled CSO discharges on aquatic ecosystems. One of the most conventional approaches is the temporary storage of excess flow in buffer tanks, followed by controlled discharge to the WWTP in dry weather. Other approaches, such as nature-based technologies, have also proven to be viable. Along with flow regulation, nature-based technologies allow water purification and habitat creation. (RIZZO et al., 2020)

The following section presents the Case Studies on CSO management, including Retention Soil Filter Compact, WWTP Smart Management, Filtration-Adsorption System, and Improved Constructed Wetland.

Retention soil filter compact

Retention Soil Filters (RSF) constitute a nature-based technology for the treatment of CSO. Their primary treatment mechanism is filtration, supported by secondary processes such as biofilm formation, sedimentation and sorption. These processes ensure the retention and partial removal of dissolved contaminants (PINNEKAMP, 2017). For instance, studies report up to 93% efficiency in the removal of suspended solids (MATZINGER et al., 2017).

RSFs consist of vegetated swales filled with filter media, such as sand, gravel, or other granular materials. As water infiltrates through the filter, vegetation and microorganisms enhance pollutant removal. The treated water is collected through drainage pipes at the base and subsequently discharged into surface water bodies (TONDERA et al., 2018). Beyond pollutant removal, RSFs also attenuate runoff peaks, mitigating hydraulic stress in receiving watercourses (MATZINGER et al., 2017).

In Aachen, Germany, a RSF was constructed at the CSO of the Soers WWTP. This RSF provides additional retention volume to the existing clarifier overflow, offering a treatment capacity of 45,000 m³ per rain event. With a total filter area of 14,600 m² (filter surface only), it is the largest RSF in Germany to date. Internal investigations by ATD GmbH estimate that its implementation will prevent the annual discharge of approximately 900,000 m³ of untreated water into receiving water bodies.

Despite these advantages, RSFs face limitations, particularly regarding space requirements. Urban development conditions often hinder stormwater management technologies from finding sufficient space, especially in densely populated regions. This restriction is one of the main reasons why the Aachen RSF differs from the standard dimensions that RSF systems usually have (GROTEHUSMANN et al., 2015). In order to achieve maximum retention capacity and reduce hydraulic stress, the system was constructed using an unconventional design approach, incorporating concrete walls to divide the RSF into six compartments, while preserving the external areas as embankments. In this study, the design applied in Aachen is referenced as the “as-built” scenario.

Building on the system applied in Aachen, further studies are being conducted to optimize space by investigating the feasibility of a compact RSF design. The aim of this approach, which is being investigated at RWTH Aachen University, is to halve the space occupied by RSFs while maintaining a pollutant removal efficiency comparable to that of conventional RSF systems. The Compact RSF method uses biofloculants to improve the aggregation of suspended solids. This enhances pollutant removal and represents a shift towards more sustainable and environmentally friendly treatment processes, as metal salt-based flocculants have conventionally been used. However, their use has had negative repercussions, such as

metal contamination of the water and the production of large quantities of sludges. In response to these problems, research is currently focused on developing innovative materials, such as biofloculants. These compounds are referred to as bio because of their biological origin and their capacity for biodegradation. (LICHTFOUSE et al., 2019)

For the Compact RSF design, the selected biofloculant is chitosan, a partially deacetylated polysaccharide derived from chitin, a biopolymer extracted from crustacean shells (LICHTFOUSE et al., 2019). The chitosan is dosed at the inlet of the channel, where a mixer disperses and homogenizes it with the CSO flow. For this configuration, the height of the filter bed must be doubled to maintain the required performance. The design may vary depending on whether concrete walls are used for the external structures or whether embankments are adopted instead. In the case of embankments, the total surface area increases. The analysis will include both scenarios to evaluate the environmental performance. The scenario with the concrete wall will be referred to as CS1e, while the scenario with the embankment will be referred to as CS1f.

Filtration-adsorption system

The filtration-adsorption system is a modular technology developed to mitigate the ecological impact of CSOs by treating wastewater before it reaches water bodies. This system consists of two complementary processes. An initial filtration process for removing suspended solids is followed by an adsorption stage targeting dissolved contaminants, such as ammonium and phosphate. The technology is being developed and tested by the University of Bologna (UNIBO). The system is currently in the pilot phase. However, the technology has been scaled up for this study to approximate its application in a full-scale scenario. Figure A 1 provides a schematic representation of the system, illustrating the main components.

The system is designed to manage CSO events dynamically, prioritizing the first hour of overflow when pollutant concentrations peak. In the full-scale application, the system manages a flow rate of 468 m³/h. During this period, a pump transfers the sewer overflow to the filtration unit, which removes most of the suspended solids. The filtration process incorporates a two-stage bag filtration system. In the first stage, a 25-micron filter removes larger particles, followed by a second 1-micron filter for finer particles. The filtered water is then stored in a buffer tank, which regulates the flow rate for the following treatment stages.

The second phase of the system utilizes eight adsorption columns connected in series to remove ammonium and phosphate. The first adsorption stage is performed using MS13X zeolite, a by-product obtained from the preparing potassium carbonate from insoluble potassium minerals through hydrothermal synthesis (ZHENG et al., 2008). Laboratory analyses conducted by the research team reported an ammonium removal efficiency of 95%. These

results align with the findings of ZHENG et al. (2008), which highlighted the significant potential of 13X zeolite as an adsorbent material for ammonium removal from aqueous solutions.

The second adsorption stage used is Sorbacid 911 Hydrotalcite, a magnesium-aluminum hydroxycarbonate. According to MADHUSUDAN et al. (2023), the hierarchical structure of hydrotalcite offers a high surface area and facilitates ion exchange, making it highly effective for phosphate recovery. This adsorption mechanism involves the incorporation of phosphate ions into the layered structure of the composite, achieving recovery efficiencies of up to 95 % during the research phase. Once adsorption is complete, the treated water is discharged into the nearest surface water body.

The filtration-adsorption system has a footprint of 75.5 m², which allows it to be installed in locations with limited space. In addition, its modular design facilitates its operation as a decentralized system that can be implemented along the sewer network. Approximately 468 m³ of water can be treated per rainfall event.

After the filtration and adsorption processes, additional stages are applied to manage by-products and support the continued functionality of the system. Once filtration is complete, the captured solids are transported to WWTP, and the used filter bags are discarded. In parallel, both adsorption materials demonstrate excellent regeneration potential, allowing up to 100 cycles before reaching irreversible depletion. Therefore, a desorption stage in a centralized plant has been integrated into the system to allow regeneration. The zeolite column is regenerated using an aqueous sodium chloride (NaCl) solution, while the hydrotalcite is regenerated using sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃). The regeneration plant includes four storage tanks, two for each adsorption material. For sodium chloride and sodium carbonate solutions, one tank stores the fresh regenerant solution, while the other collects the spent solution after it has passed through the adsorption columns.

Two operational scenarios are addressed in the study. The first scenario involves reusing the desorption solution, allowing up to 10 regeneration cycles per load before replacement (CS2d). The second involves non-recycling of the desorption solution, which is discarded after each use (CS2e).

Wastewater treatment plant smart management

Wastewater treatment plants often exceed their operational capacity during wet weather seasons. In order to address this challenge, forecasting strategies can be used to anticipate high inflow events and thus optimize performance. The Birs WWTP (Switzerland) faces similar obstacles and, over the years, has progressively optimized its operation to improve its performance under these conditions. The facility operates using a sequential batch reactor (SBR) system, which, as opposed to conventional systems that physically separate the

different treatment stages, integrates the entire process in a single reactor, performing programmed sequences in operational cycles (STEINEMANN and KOCH, 2016).

Improvements include the development of a dynamic SBR cycle optimized with nitrate gradient, as well as tools based on weather forecasts. The plant employs precipitation radar technology to improve its hydraulic operation during rainfall events. The data obtained are integrated into an automated system that estimates the risk of precipitation based on the expected probability and intensity (STÖCKLIN et al., 2021). Thus, filling, treatment, and discharge are executed dynamically without fixed time intervals. As part of the StopUP project, the University of Applied Sciences Northwestern Switzerland (FHNW) team evaluates the benefits and limitations of rainfall radar forecasting, as well as proposes improvements in the control of the treatment plant during wet weather conditions through smart Real-Time Control (RTC) and the use of sensors distributed in the catchment area and in the facility itself.

The plant is sized for 150,000 population equivalents, with a capacity of 500 L/s in dry flow conditions that can be increased to 1,000 L/s during wet weather, providing a maximum of 20 continuous hours of operation during these peaks. The adoption of the dynamic controller resulted in the treatment of an additional average of 800,000 m³ of water per year. Thus, it represents an effective solution to address the increasing frequency of runoff and CSO events.

The technology applies to other plants based on SBR processes that aim to optimize their performance in wet weather conditions. The main advantage is the potential of using existing structures since optimization is achieved through software and operational adjustments.

Throughout this study, this alternative is considered not only under case study 3 but also incorporated as a reference scenario in the other analyses (scenario c). Hence, the potential environmental impacts associated with treating the additional inflows at a plant can be evaluated by operating as a combined sewer overflow (CSO) mitigation technology.

Improved constructed wetland

In recent decades, constructed wetlands have emerged as an effective alternative for treating pollutants from point and diffuse sources (ZHANG et al., 2022), including stormwater runoff, urban wastewater, and agricultural effluents. The principle of operation is based on the simulation of natural wetland processes. Plants favor the development of microbial communities that, through a series of biogeochemical processes, contribute to transforming and removing pollutants from the water (DAVIS, 1995). These advantages, coupled with relatively low construction and operating costs, have positioned artificial wetlands as a viable and efficient solution for stormwater treatment (GATO-TRINIDAD et al., 2023).

The Higher Institute of Applied Biological Sciences of Tunis (ISSBAT) studies this technology as a viable solution for restoring and mitigating environmental pressures on the Sebkhia Sijoumi wetland, which has been subjected to significant and fluctuating anthropogenic stressors. It is located in the southwest of the Greater Tunis metropolitan area, in a densely populated urban area, further aggravating its vulnerability. In particular, the ecosystem faces progressive deterioration due to the constant discharge of untreated wastewater, which has increased with urban growth and the irregular settlement of polluting industries.

In Tunis, a semi-pilot plant based on a hybrid constructed wetland technology has been adopted. The first stage integrates a vertical subsurface flow constructed wetland (VFCW), followed by a second stage with a horizontal subsurface flow constructed wetlands (HFCW). Each wetland configuration provides distinct benefits, allowing their advantages to complement each other and mitigating the individual limitations of each system. The HFCWs are highly effective in removing the biological oxygen demand (BOD₅) and suspended solids (TSS) in secondary treatment. However, their limited oxygen transfer capacity mainly restricts biological processes to anaerobic conditions, impeding, i.e., nitrification. In contrast, VFCWs have a higher oxygenation capacity, favoring the development of aerobic processes, improving nitrification efficiency, and requiring less space compared to HFCWs. (UN-HABITAT, 2008)

In addition to the constructed wetlands system, an adsorption column filled with clay and biochar composite materials has been integrated and targeted explicitly to remove bisphenol A and diclofenac. However, since the columns are still in the early stages of development, they are not suitable for direct comparison with more established treatment technologies. Consequently, the environmental assessment primarily focuses on the constructed wetland, which has already been validated in practical applications (RIZZO et al., 2020). For this purpose, the system is scaled to actual conditions, considering a defined flow rate and specific water quality parameters. This case study will be referred to as CS6d.

2.1.2 Sustainable drainage systems

An additional strategy for CSO mitigation starts even before the runoff reaches the sewer system. To this end, decentralized solutions, such as green infrastructure, are implemented within sustainable drainage systems (SuDS) (QUARANTA et al., 2022b). SuDS represent a fundamental shift towards nature-based water management, integrating ecological principles to address the challenges of urbanization and climate change (MONACHESE et al., 2025).

The integration of SuDS provides stormwater storage and filtration. Their ability to regulate runoff volumes reduces pressure on conventional drainage infrastructures, decreases peak discharges, and contributes to mitigating the risk of flooding downstream (GIMENEZ-MARANGES

et al., 2020). Three case studies on the application of runoff treatment technologies are presented below: gravel and sand filters, seashell infiltration systems, and bioretention cells.

Gravel and sand filter

Sand filters are stormwater management systems designed to treat runoff through a sandy media. Their typical configuration includes two main components, a sedimentation pond and a sand filtration unit. The sedimentation pond is a pretreatment stage where larger particles and suspended materials are retained, thus reducing the solids entering the sand filter. After the sedimentation stage is completed, the pre-treated water flows to the filtration unit, passing through a sand bed that facilitates the removal of finer suspended solids, nutrients, metals, and other contaminants. This process is based on physical, adsorption, and biological mechanisms within the filter media. (NCDEQ, 2018b)

In the landscape park, Wolvenberg in Antwerp, Belgium, a sand and gravel filter has been installed to treat urban runoff from a 3.8-hectare catchment area composed of high-traffic roads and residential zones. The rainwater collected from this area is first directed to a 560 m³ sedimentation pond, constructed with bentonite mats to prevent uncontrolled infiltration before undergoing sand and gravel filter treatment. Following filtration, the treated water infiltrates two swales. Implementing the filter is expected to improve water quality and mitigate the risk of flooding downstream. The main objective of the filter will be to reduce suspended solids and thus remove metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) attached to these solids. However, the performance is also limited. The system is ineffective in the presence of influents heavily loaded with nutrients.

The gravel and sand filter technology is assessed through LCA to determine its environmental impact. To ensure comparability with the other case studies, the system has been resized and adapted to homogeneous conditions while preserving its fundamental operating principles. Within this study, the system will be identified as CS4a.

Urban rain shell

Seashells in stormwater treatment have emerged as a technology for removing pollutants. The motivations for its implementation are not limited to treatment efficiency but also the use and revaluation of marine resources. Shells are waste from the seafood processing industry and find an extension of their life cycle in water treatment (CURRIE et al., 2007). Due to the high calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) content and porous structure, seashells exhibit strong adsorption capacity and ion exchange potential, enhancing the removal and retention of contaminants, particularly heavy metals (XU et al., 2021).

Recent studies have found that seashells effectively remove copper, cadmium, and zinc, reaching removal rates of up to 93% in the case of zinc (BREMNER et al., 2020; CHARTERS et al., 2021a). Most studies are still in the laboratory phase and focus primarily on the removal of heavy metals. Other research has explored the potential for phosphate elimination (PARADELO et al., 2016). In this regard, CURRIE et al. (2007) reported that materials derived from calcined shells (lime) can achieve up to 90% phosphate removal, while unprocessed shells reach approximately 40%. Despite these findings, research on the performance of shells in removing pathogens, nitrogen, and other contaminants remains limited.

An example of a large-scale application is the Urban Rain Shell (URS) technology by Aquafin, installed in Wetteren, Belgium. The system combines the storage and purification of rainwater using a subsurface bed of shells (AA EcoShells) and a mineral filter (AA Minerals). Its design allows the removal of heavy metals, mineral oils, PAHs, and other organic pollutants, enabling the treated water to be reused, infiltrated or discharged into surface water bodies.

The system collects runoff from a 0.6 ha impervious catchment from store roofs and car parks. After pre-treatment, the water is distributed into the system through a supply drain surrounded by EcoShells AA. As it flows, suspended solids and contaminants are retained in the filter layers. Finally, the treated water passes through a mineral mix (AA Minerals), is collected in the outlet drain, and can be reused for landscape irrigation or recreational purposes. This technology will be referred to as CS4b throughout the study.

Bioretention cell

Bioretention cells (BRCs) constitute a widely adopted practice for sustainable urban drainage (KÖIV-VAINIK et al., 2022). These systems consist of a vegetated depression filled with an engineered porous substrate that intercepts, filters, stores, and treats polluted runoff (EPA, 2021). The filter substrate consists of a mixture of sand, organic matter, silt, and clay, providing high permeability. The system includes a mulch and a ponding layer with vegetation (KÖIV-VAINIK et al., 2022). Each component of the BRC performs a function in the treatment process. Temporary storage occurs in the ponding zone, where water infiltrates the soil or evaporates while suspended particles settle out. Plant litter and mulch contribute to the filtration of pollutants and create a medium for micro-organisms that can degrade hydrocarbons and other pollutants. The clay soils in the mixture increase the retention of heavy metals. In addition, plant roots absorb the moisture retained in the soil pores, promoting vegetation growth and supporting the phytoremediation process (COOK, 2007).

The size of bioretention cells is determined by the drainage area and the volume of runoff generated (EPA, 2021). In addition, these systems usually have underdrains connected to the storm drainage network, allowing excess water management in case of overflow (KÖIV-VAINIK

et al., 2022). Bioretention systems have demonstrated high efficiency in removing total suspended solids (TSS) and total volatile solids (TVS). However, one of their main limitations is the low efficiency in removing dissolved nutrients, particularly nitrates and phosphates (TIRPAK et al., 2021).

The BRC under study is located in Trondheim, Norway, and was designed for a return period of 20 years, with a concentration-time of 10 minutes and a climate factor of 1.4 (ARNTSEN STRØMBERG, M., 11.11.2024). The bioretention substrate comprises 73% sand, 21% silt, and 6% clay. The system captures runoff generated by a 550 m² car park and a solar panel roof of approximately 340 m². The BRC has a surface area of 50 m² and a total depth of 80 cm, distributed over 30 cm of substrate, 30 cm of drainage layer, and 20 cm of crushed stone. The system is placed close to a detention tank, thus controlling excess water by draining it into the tank through a drainage system. Throughout the analysis, this system will be referred to as CS5.

2.2 Sustainability of materials and services

Concrete and steel are the most used materials in the construction sector worldwide. Increasing demand and high energy consumption in their production increase resource depletion and concern sustainable development (MEHRA et al., 2022). The production of steel (32 MJ/kg) and concrete (1.9 MJ/kg) requires large amounts of energy, thus becoming significant sources of CO₂ emissions (NIDHEESH and KUMAR, 2019; MEHRA et al., 2022). These materials are also essential for stormwater management technologies, providing the structural integrity and durability required. Due to their mechanical properties, replacement is not an option in the short term until other alternatives have been evaluated and validated. Assessing the impact provides insight into their effects and identifies areas for improvement (ZABALZA BRIBIÁN et al., 2011).

The following provides an overview of the environmental impact of the different materials and services required over the lifetime of the studied technologies. It also provides background for understanding the relationship to the impact categories discussed in the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) in Chapter 5.

2.2.1 Materials for construction and operation

The impact categories selected for the analysis of the technologies are detailed in the appendix in Table D 1, indicating the nature of each category and the environmental implications. These are Climate Change (GWP), Acidification Potential (TAP), Eutrophication Freshwater (FEP) and Marine (MEP), Ecotoxicity Freshwater (FETP) and Marine (METP), and Water Use (WCP). The same categories are used in this section to differentiate materials according to their environmental footprint.

Considering the wide selection of impact categories, a more representative approach to show the environmental implications of materials is through a brief comparative analysis and further explanation of the main contributors within the materials value chain to the overall impact. To this end, the absolute impact of materials is first shown for each impact category, incorporating the impact factors. Then, the values are normalized to identify the materials with the highest impact.

Table 2.1 lists materials and their contribution to each impact category. All impact factors are from ecoinvent v3.10 and have been selected only from this database to ensure conformity. The specific material flows used are detailed in Table C 18 and Table C 19.

From the values in Table 2.1, it is not easy to identify or have a reference to indicate the impact of one material relative to another. Therefore, the values are adjusted to the same scale as a second step to understand the relative impact contributions. The values in each category are normalized by dividing each impact factor by the maximum factor within the same category. This indicates dimensionless scores ranging from 0 to 1, where the material with the highest impact is attributed a value of 1, and all other materials are represented in relative proportion to this maximum. Table 2.2 presents the ranking by a color gradient, where green indicates the lowest impact, orange-yellow medium values, and red the highest environmental footprint.

Table 2.1: Environmental impact factors of materials for the construction and operation of stormwater treatment systems

Material [kg]	Impact category	Climate change [kg CO2-Eq]	Acidification potential [kg SO2-Eq]	Freshwater eutrophication [kg P-Eq]	Marine eutrophication [kg N-Eq]	Freshwater ecotoxicity [kg 1.4-DCB-Eq]	Marine ecotoxicity [kg 1.4-DCB-Eq]	Water use [m ³]
Concrete		1.54E-01	3.12E-04	2.01E-06	5.70E-07	9.80E-05	9.75E-04	4.35E-04
Reinforcing steel		2.29E+00	5.45E-03	9.60E-05	5.53E-05	1.64E-02	5.45E-01	2.13E-02
Stainless steel		5.43E+00	1.95E-02	2.02E-04	8.13E-05	1.54E-02	3.83E-01	3.75E-02
Cast iron		1.66E+00	3.91E-03	8.10E-05	7.51E-06	2.58E-02	7.69E-01	7.54E-03
Polyethylene		2.53E+00	4.96E-03	5.11E-05	5.20E-05	2.03E-03	2.78E-02	1.50E-02
Polyvinyl chloride		3.05E+00	8.14E-03	1.12E-04	1.00E-04	2.95E-03	2.93E-02	1.90E-02
Polypropylene		2.48E+00	4.77E-03	4.73E-05	5.23E-05	1.96E-03	2.64E-02	1.21E-02
Electrical wiring		6.44E+00	2.85E-01	1.71E-03	2.99E-04	5.02E-02	4.63E-01	1.03E-01
Tap water		3.08E-04	1.09E-06	1.99E-08	3.55E-09	9.55E-07	2.49E-05	3.44E-06
Flocculant		5.49E-01	2.49E-03	4.62E-05	2.33E-05	1.20E-03	1.31E-02	7.95E-03
Calcium carbonate		2.41E-03	2.84E-05	2.20E-08	3.36E-08	1.64E-06	3.66E-05	8.58E-05
Sand		2.28E-03	1.03E-05	3.52E-08	2.78E-08	3.65E-06	8.40E-05	3.59E-05
Crushed gravel		3.68E-03	1.69E-05	8.14E-08	5.40E-08	8.95E-06	2.07E-04	3.66E-04
Bentonite		4.05E-02	1.81E-04	1.10E-06	7.85E-07	7.44E-05	6.52E-04	3.98E-04
Sodium chloride		1.50E-01	7.99E-04	1.73E-05	2.50E-05	3.44E-04	3.66E-03	3.40E-03
Sodium carbonate		9.41E-01	9.29E-03	1.10E-04	7.14E-05	1.53E-03	1.50E-02	4.90E-02

Table 2.2: Normalized impact factors of materials

Material	GWP	TAP	FEP	MEP	FETP	METP	WCP
Concrete	0.02398	0.00110	0.00118	0.00191	0.00195	0.00127	0.00422
Reinforcing steel	0.35482	0.01912	0.05620	0.18494	0.32627	0.70888	0.20671
Stainless steel	0.84340	0.06848	0.11824	0.27208	0.30696	0.49895	0.36339
Cast iron	0.25817	0.01374	0.04744	0.02512	0.51367	1.00000	0.07307
Polyethylene	0.39265	0.01742	0.02992	0.17401	0.04042	0.03615	0.14523
Polyvinyl chloride	0.47316	0.02858	0.06567	0.33456	0.05877	0.03813	0.18389
Polypropylene	0.38467	0.01675	0.02769	0.17487	0.03911	0.03430	0.11716
Electrical wiring	1.00000	1.00000	1.00000	1.00000	1.00000	0.60210	1.00000
Tap water	0.00005	0.00000	0.00001	0.00001	0.00002	0.00003	0.00003
Flocculant	0.08530	0.00873	0.02708	0.07781	0.02397	0.01703	0.07707
Calcium carbonate	0.00037	0.00010	0.00001	0.00011	0.00003	0.00005	0.00083
Sand	0.00035	0.00004	0.00002	0.00009	0.00007	0.00011	0.00035
Crushed gravel	0.00057	0.00006	0.00005	0.00018	0.00018	0.00027	0.00355
Bentonite	0.00629	0.00064	0.00064	0.00263	0.00148	0.00085	0.00385
Sodium chloride	0.02321	0.00280	0.01011	0.08373	0.00685	0.00476	0.03297
Sodium carbonate	0.14610	0.03260	0.06440	0.23892	0.03048	0.01946	0.47524

According to the heat map, metals show the highest environmental impacts, with electrical wiring having the most significant burdens in almost all categories due to its copper content. It is followed by cast iron, stainless steel, and reinforcing steel. Plastics, flocculants, sodium chloride, and sodium carbonate have intermediate values. Aggregates like sand, crushed gravel, and bentonite show relatively low impacts. As for concrete, despite being a widely used material, it presents low impacts compared to the other materials analyzed.

The main processes contributing to the environmental impact of the materials considered are discussed below. The overview is structured according to the following groups of materials: metals, plastics, aggregates, and concrete. In addition, a subchapter dedicated to the bioflocculant chitosan is included. It was not considered in the previous normalization due to the significant uncertainties regarding the degree of development of the technology for its production.

Metals

The mining industry is one of the sectors with the highest energy consumption and, consequently, one of the main sources of CO₂ emissions. The impact is intensified by the increasing demand for raw materials and the declining ore grades (the proportion of metal within the extracted mineral), requiring the extraction and processing of larger volumes of minerals to obtain the same amount of metal (ELSHKAKI et al., 2016; NORTHEY et al., 2014; SANJUAN-DELMÁS et al., 2022). Ore depletion results in higher diesel and explosives consumption in the mine and higher water and energy consumption in the processing facilities (NORGATE and JAHANSHAHI, 2010). Moreover, there is also an increased generation of waste and an alteration of the local habitat (NORTHEY et al., 2014). Mining is especially evident in the case of copper (LU et al., 2022).

Smelting is another central process in metal production. It is energy-intensive, mainly due to its high-temperature requirements. In the case of steel, it represents the main source of environmental impact (HU et al., 2006).

Strategies such as recycling and process optimization are required to reduce the environmental burden (HARPPRECHT et al., 2024). Ferrous metals, for instance, are recyclable; approximately 75% of the raw materials used come from scrap (LAMBERT, 2016). Similarly, copper recycling has considerable environmental performance compared to primary refining. HONG et al. (2018) found that recovered copper scenarios had between 59% and 99% less environmental impacts.

Besides recycling, improvements in process efficiency can further reduce the carbon footprint. Minimizing direct emissions of heavy metals to air and water, increasing energy efficiency, transitioning from fossil fuel to renewable energy sources, and maximizing ore extraction and material consumption reduce the overall footprint (HONG et al., 2018; HU et al., 2006).

Plastics

Within the materials used in the construction and operation of stormwater treatment technologies, three main polymers can be identified: polyethylene (PE), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), and polypropylene (PP). These plastics, derived from petroleum and known as conventional plastics, account for 4% to 8% of annual global petroleum consumption (WALKER and ROTHMAN, 2020). Their carbon footprint is linked to the energy-intensive processes required to transform fossil fuels into plastic resins, which are then processed into plastic products (ZAPPITELLI et al., 2021).

These plastics are mainly used in pipes, pond liners, and geotextiles, among other components. According to the comparison of the three polymers presented in Table 2.2, PVC has a higher impact. This result is in line with ALSABRI and AL-GHAMDI (2020). Regarding transformation processes, NAEEM et al. (2023) identified extrusion as the main contributor to emissions.

Plastics have been replacing other materials due to their low weight, corrosion resistance, and processing at lower temperatures (WALKER and ROTHMAN, 2020). However, their disposal remains a concern due to their slow degradation rate, leading to the propagation of microplastics and macroplastics in both marine and freshwater ecosystems (LI et al., 2018). Incorporating recycling into the production chain is a primary approach to reduce environmental pollution and promote production efficiency (ALSABRI and AL-GHAMDI, 2020; NAEEM et al., 2023).

Aggregates

Natural aggregates, such as gravel and sand, are main components of concrete and thus present in nearly all built structures (LANGER, 2016). In stormwater treatment technologies, they are not only used in concrete but also serve as filter media.

Although the overall contribution of aggregate extraction to resource depletion, land use competition, global warming, and energy consumption is relatively low (BLEISCHWITZ and BAHN-WALKOWIAK, 2006), its production is not exempt from environmental impacts. The extraction and processing of aggregates result in landscape alterations, dust emissions, noise pollution, vibrations from blasting, and potential degradation of surface and groundwater bodies. Furthermore, when transportation impacts are considered, the environmental burden increases significantly due to the large volumes of material. (LANGER, 2016)

Eventually, the exploitation of aggregate deposits will lead to the depletion of deposits and the closure of quarries. In response, several secondary materials have proven viable alternatives to replace natural aggregates partially. These include construction and demolition waste, seashells, slag, perlite, and recycled glass. (LANGER, 2016)

Concrete

Concrete is one of the most used building materials worldwide and represents an important source of CO₂ emissions (FLATT et al., 2012). As part of the concrete production cycle, between 74 % and 81 % of total CO₂ emissions are attributed to cement manufacturing (SONEBI et al., 2016). Due to the high production volume, the cement industry is responsible for 6 % to 8 % of global CO₂ emissions (CAVALETT et al., 2024; FLATT et al., 2012). These emissions originate predominantly from two sources: the decarbonation of calcium carbonate during the calcination process and emissions from the combustion of fossil fuels to reach the necessary temperatures in the kilns (ALI et al., 2011; FLATT et al., 2012; KHAIYUM et al., 2023).

In addition to cement production, the second most significant source of CO₂ emissions in concrete production comes from the aggregates acquisition. Regarding environmental impact, the most significant factor is not the extraction or production of the aggregates themselves but their transport, on account of the volume of material moved and the distances required. (SONEBI et al., 2016)

Several strategies have been developed to mitigate the environmental burdens associated with concrete, particularly cement. Among them are the partial substitution of clinker for supplementary materials, the optimization of fuel usage in production processes, the recycling of concrete from demolition, and the implementation of carbon capture and storage technologies (CAVALETT et al., 2024; FLATT et al., 2012).

Chitosan

Chitosan is an alternative to recover shrimp shell waste. However, its production generates significant environmental effects that need to be assessed to establish its potential as a sustainable resource (VICENTE et al., 2024).

According to VICENTE et al. (2024), chitosan production generates a carbon footprint ranging from 184 to 1891 kg CO₂ eq. per kilogram of chitosan. In contrast, a study by RIOFRIO et al. (2021) reported a lower value of 59 kg CO₂ eq. The discrepancy in the reported values is mainly associated with the technology used for the transformation and the performance of the process. Although the value reported by RIOFRIO et al. (2021) is lower than that reported by VICENTE et al. (2024), both figures reflect a high ecological burden.

The two studies identified the leading causes. These include the intensive use of chemical reagents such as acids, NaOH, and ethanol, the high energy demand during key steps such as extraction, agitation, and deacetylation, and emissions related to waste management and transport.

2.2.2 Services for construction and operation

The environmental impact of the construction sector is not only related to the production and use of materials but also involves their transportation to the construction sites (ESTOKOVA et al., 2017). Similarly, energy consumption during the operational phase represents another relevant impact source. An overview of the services is presented below.

Transportation

Emissions from freight transport are determined by the type of fuel used, whether diesel, gasoline, or electricity (MCKINNON et al., 2010). Furthermore, location, vehicle size, technological choice, production process, and fuel efficiency influence greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (MACHADO et al., 2021).

Diesel and gasoline contain hydrogen and carbon and, due to incomplete combustion, generate emissions of hydrocarbons, carbon monoxide, and nitrogen oxides (MCKINNON et al., 2010). Regarding transportation by electric power, the environmental impact is directly determined by the energy mix, given that the electricity generation varies significantly depending on the combination of sources used (MACHADO et al., 2021).

For reference, a 16-32 metric ton diesel truck has an estimated impact of 194.57 g CO₂-eq per ton-kilometer (tkm) transported (ecoinvent v3.10). A comparative study by SCHULTE and NY (2018) on electric trucks powered by different energy sources revealed that electricity generated from coal generates the highest emissions (229 g CO₂-eq/tkm), followed by

electricity with the EU energy mix (117 g CO₂-eq/tkm) and, finally, electricity generated by wind power, which represents the cleanest option with only 31 g CO₂-eq/tkm.

Electricity

The environmental impact of electricity production depends on the source of energy used. According to GHISELLINI et al. (2023), fossil fuels have the highest impact. Coal is the most intensive, with 1.14 kg CO₂-eq/kWh, followed by fuel oil with 0.902 kg CO₂-eq/kWh. Natural gas has a lower impact with 0.684 kg CO₂-eq/kWh.

By contrast, the contribution of renewable energy sources is much lower. Solar photovoltaic energy has a GWP of 0.0657 kg CO₂-eq/kWh, while geothermal energy shows a similar value with 0.0627 kg CO₂-eq/kWh. Hydropower generates a slightly higher impact of 0.0901 kg CO₂-eq/kWh. Among all options, onshore wind energy stands out as the most environmentally friendly, with an impact of 0.0258 kg CO₂ eq/kWh. (GHISELLINI et al., 2023)

3 Methodology

Multiple assessment tools have emerged to quantify the impacts of materials, services, and processes. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) has been established as a core methodology to identify the trade-offs within a value chain (HELLWEG and LLORENÇ MILÀ I CANALS, 2014). In this study, LCA is applied to the technologies described in Chapter 2.1.

The methodology includes the definition of scenarios for each case study, with a description of the water quality parameters considered and the dimensioning. Then, the LCA is performed for the corresponding configurations, assessing the environmental impacts under typical conditions.

3.1 Scenarios definition

The LCA is structured in three separate assessments, each focusing on different groups of technologies. These groups are analyzed independently, as their different objectives and application contexts make direct comparisons unfeasible. Within each group, a comparison with baseline scenarios is also provided:

- Scenario A (No Intervention): Direct discharge of untreated water into the receiving environment.
- Scenario B (WWTP): Treatment of water in a wastewater treatment plant without exceeding its capacity.
- Scenario C (Storage Tank + WWTP): Use of a storage tank to control the flow before sending the water to a WWTP under dry weather conditions.

For consistency purposes with the nomenclature used in the StopUP project and to avoid confusion, the technologies evaluated preserve the same designations assigned within the project. Thus, each case study (CS) has its original denomination. In addition, within each case study, different scenarios are analyzed, each identified by a specific letter. For instance, while CS1 refers to the Retention Soil Filter (RSF) in the original classification, in this study, CS1a represents the No Intervention scenario, serving as one of the comparative baselines for this technology.

3.1.1 Combined sewer overflow treatment

Mean concentration scenarios

The first group of technologies for CSO management is focused on treating flows with average pollutant concentrations. This group comprises three case studies: CS1: Soil Retention Filter, CS3: Smart WWTP Management, and CS6: Improved Constructed Wetland.

While CS1 and CS3 maintain their original configurations and operate with the actual volumes entering the systems under normal conditions, CS6 requires sizing and adaptation to the established inlet concentrations. The assumptions and sizing criteria used for the technologies are presented in section 3.4.8. In total, this group considers 13 scenarios, presented in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Framework of case studies and scenarios for managing CSOs for mean concentrations

Peak concentration scenarios

The second group focuses on the CS2, filtration-adsorption system, evaluated under peak rather than average concentration conditions. The analysis follows the same methodology established for Group 1, by comparing the technology with the three baseline scenarios. Additionally, two technological variations are included. Figure 3.2 presents the defined scenarios, which will be referenced throughout the analysis.

Figure 3.2: Framework of case study and scenarios for managing CSOs for peak concentrations

Water quality

Water quality in CSO events varies considerably and is influenced by numerous factors affecting the composition and concentrations of contaminants. The heterogeneity is not only observed between single events but also within the same event, in different seasons, and in different catchment areas (TONDERA et al., 2018). Factors such as land use, climatic conditions, and the configuration of combined sewer systems significantly influence the pollutant loads present in water (BAUM et al., 2021; RIZZO et al., 2020; SANDOVAL et al., 2013).

The scientific literature indicates this variability through the wide ranges of concentrations recorded for key water quality indicators such as total suspended solids (TSS), chemical oxygen demand (COD), nutrients, and heavy metals. In the case of TSS, concentrations can range from minimum values of 13 mg/L to maximum values exceeding 1,400 mg/L (MÉTADIER and BERTRAND-KRAJEWSKI, 2012).

Similarly, COD shows a significant variability, with mean values ranging from 112 mg/L to 274 mg/L (SEIBERT and RASEL, 2004). For nutrients, reported values for total nitrogen (TN) range from 7 mg/L to 12.6 mg/L (BROMBACH et al., 2005; NICKEL et al., 2021), while total phosphorus (TP) ranges from 0.92 mg/L to 3.01 mg/L (NICKEL et al., 2021; SEIBERT and RASEL, 2004).

Table A 3 presents the water quality parameters used for the comparative assessment of the CSO treatment technologies under average and maximum concentration conditions. The table integrates the data from Group 1 and Group 2 technologies. While the values for the average concentrations are based on a literature review with commonly recorded pollutant levels, the values for the maximum concentrations are derived from measurements provided by the researchers involved in developing the filtration-adsorption system.

In order to ensure comparison between the technologies in Group 1, proxy values were defined to reflect the variability of the reported concentrations. Therefore, the data obtained in the case

studies were first reviewed regarding system conditions. These values were then compared with the available literature to identify appropriate ranges. As a result of this process, the values presented in Table A 3 in the Appendix were selected. It should be noted that the case study values were used exclusively for the review and were not provided for publication or external dissemination.

In cases of uncertainty in the reported values, a conservative approach was prioritized, especially for parameters such as TSS and COD, which showed larger deviations from the documented ranges. Higher values were adopted in these situations to reflect more demanding design conditions. This approach has been supported in methodological discussions (RHEMY, C., 20.12.2024). The sources considered in this analysis are detailed for all pollutants studied in Table A 2 in the Appendix.

3.1.2 Urban runoff management

The third group consists of technologies for urban runoff management, which are evaluated and compared against the three previously defined baseline scenarios. Unlike the other groups, the three technologies are dimensioned under the same conditions, allowing for a direct performance comparison. In total, six scenarios are analyzed. Figure 3.3 provides a reference for the evaluated scenarios.

Figure 3.3: Framework of case studies and scenarios for urban runoff management

Standardization and hydraulic design parameters

Stormwater runoff management technologies were initially designed for specific contexts and catchment areas (Table A 1). However, these technologies have been adapted and scaled to a standard system for simplified comparison. This approach is based on standardized parameters, including a normative flow rate and typical characteristics of the pollutants in the influent water. These adjustments also allow for a fair comparison within the LCA, ensuring that all systems perform similar functions, in other words, retention, and enhancement of water quality for discharge or infiltration into the water bodies.

To ensure uniformity in the comparison, a representative model site has been selected in Europe, with an average annual precipitation of 800 mm. A system with an area of 4,400 m² was selected to represent typical urban catchment conditions, equivalent to the average size of a city block, with approximate dimensions of 65 x 65 m (MAJOR, 2015). The scenario represents a highly impervious surface of parking lots, paved streets, and a densely populated residential area. The surfaces have extremely low permeability, resulting in a runoff coefficient of 0.9, which implies that 90% of rainwater is directed into the drainage systems (HALAMA et al., 2023).

The mean annual precipitation in the study area was estimated at 800 mm, which is consistent with the European average of 829 mm reported in 2020 (THEGLOBALECONOMY, 2020). Interannual fluctuations are minimal, which reinforces the representativeness of this value as a basis for design.

The hydraulic design is based on a return period of 5 years, following the German technical guidelines of DWA-A 117:2013 (Guidelines for Infiltration Systems) (DWA, 2013). This period is aligned with the protection category “moderate,” defined in the DWA-A 138-1, which establishes a minimum rainfall frequency of once every five years. This category considers urban areas where flooding can cause minor or moderate damage without compromising safety or health, such as residential dwellings, commercial spaces, and parking lots (DWA, 2024). Within this study, this classification is used to reflect realistic conditions relevant to the context being evaluated.

The impact of climate change on precipitation events with a return period of five years is a concern for infrastructure design. According to WILLEMS (2013), to maintain design standards under future climate scenarios, storage capacity should be increased from 150 m³/ha (15 mm) to 300-400 m³/ha (30-40 mm). Therefore, a design intensity of 40 mm/h is considered in this study, anticipating the conditions projected by climate change.

In the standardization process, key physical parameters were ensured in line with the DWA-A138-1. The guidelines stipulate a minimum distance of 1 m between the base of the infiltration system and the water table, in addition to the need for a soil permeability coefficient of at least 1×10^{-6} m/s to ensure optimum performance (DWA, 2024). With this permeability coefficient, the initial infiltration rate is approximately $I=3.6$ mm/h, considering ideal conditions, such as unobstructed vertical flow and unsaturated soil. This assumption reflects idealized conditions. However, this work determines the system dimensions based on buffer capacity and treatment performance without considering actual infiltration conditions. It is assumed that all water falling in the catchment area will drain directly into the technology, allowing it to collect and manage the total runoff generated during rainfall events.

The volume of water generated during an event with a return period of five years and an intensity of 40 mm/h represents 158.4 m³, corresponding to the maximum volume considered for the design of the systems. Furthermore, these systems provide an annual management capacity of 3,168 m³. Table A 6 details the hydrological parameters and characteristics of the system.

CS4a: Gravel and sand filter

The original system was designed for a larger catchment area than the one analyzed in this study. In order to adapt it to the specific site conditions, the system was scaled proportionally, preserving the filter-to-buffer ratio at 9 to 1 (VAN DEN BROECK, N., 13.12.2024). With this ratio, the storage capacity of the filter and the required size of the upstream buffer were calculated. Following the original design, the filter maintains a filtration layer of 70 cm, which facilitates transversal flow. Once the water passes through the filter, it is directed to the swale, where infiltration into the soil takes place.

The resizing maintains the effectiveness of the system in handling high-intensity rainfall events (up to 40 mm/h) without including a second gutter for peak rainfall management, as in the original design. The characteristics of the system, both before the resizing and in its scaled version, are detailed in Table A 8 of the Appendix.

CS4b: Urban Rain Shell Filter

The system was initially designed with the objective of water reuse. However, within the StopUP project, this objective was redefined to focus on infiltration and preventing surface and groundwater contamination. Consequently, modifications were introduced to the original design. A key aspect of these adjustments is the life cycle of the filtration material, which is determined by its adsorption capacity for heavy metals, reaching its limit after treating a specific volume of water (PANNEKOEK, G., 14.11.2024).

Rather than designing the system based on the periodic replacement of the filtration material, the approach adopted in this study consists of incorporating the total required amount of materials from the beginning and ensuring treatment efficiency over 30 years while reducing maintenance frequency and associated costs. However, this design choice results in an increase in the surface area required for implementation.

The storage capacity of the system was calculated based on the porosity of the filter media, assuming 30% for minerals and 65% for shells. According to the specifications of the supplier, the inclusion of a sedimentation tank is necessary to avoid clogging and to distribute the water through the filter evenly. Consequently, this pretreatment unit, with a volume of 9 m³, has been incorporated. Table A 9 presents the characterization of the system after sizing.

CS5: Bioretention Cell

In the configuration of the bioretention cell (BRC) located in Trondheim, it was identified that the priority of the system lies in water treatment. However, structural modifications were made to facilitate comparison with other case studies and allow control of the drainage rate. Thus, a sizing concept based on pore storage was applied, which allows the system to fulfill both functions. Two main modifications were implemented to the original configuration of the BRC:

- Inclusion of a ponding layer

A surface storage layer was incorporated to enhance drainage regulation and optimize system efficiency. For its construction, an earthen embankment was chosen over concrete walls, aligning with a Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) approach.

- Increased filter media depth

The depth of the engineered soil was increased from 30 cm to 60 cm, providing additional infiltration capacity. As a result of this adjustment, the BRC becomes more effective at filtering stormwater from rooftops and paved surfaces, consistent with research suggesting that a 60 - cm soil layer provides better pollutant retention and long-term vegetative stability (BROWN and HUNT, 2011).

The designed filter media is composed of a mixture of sand (73%), silt (21%), and clay (6%), corresponding to a sandy loam soil with an infiltration rate of 20 to 30 mm/h (PATLE et al., 2019). This composition allows it to manage precipitation events of up to 40 mm/h. This process is favored by the ponding layer upstream of the filter, buffering the water flow before treatment.

A 7.5 cm mulch layer was added to improve the retention of fine particles and organic matter (WILLARD et al., 2017). Also, a 40 cm gravel layer was placed at the base of the system to optimize drainage and facilitate water transport to the deeper soil layers.

The total storage capacity of the system was determined by considering the volumetric contributions of each of its functional layers (ponding, mulch, filter media, and gravel). The area required to comply with the normative volume regulation was calculated from this total volume, resulting in an area of 262.99 m². A detailed breakdown of the BRC design parameters can be found in Appendix Table A 11.

Water quality

Pollutant concentrations in runoff are not characterized by a single value and depend on several factors, including the use and characteristics of the impervious surface. In general, traffic areas have significantly higher pollutant loads than residential areas. Road and parking

lot surfaces, regardless of traffic intensity or vehicle type, have generated higher TSS loads than roofs (GÖBEL et al., 2007). In residential areas, where runoff comes mainly from roofs, the concentration of pollutants varies depending on the type of material used. For instance, the presence of metals such as zinc or copper in runoff depends on whether the roof material is coated or not and its service life (CHARTERS et al., 2021b; GÖBEL et al., 2007). Even within areas with the same use, pollutant concentrations can differ substantially due to different construction materials. As reported by MÜLLER et al. (2020), pollution sources in stormwater can be classified into three main compartments: atmospheric deposition, drainage surfaces, and anthropogenic activities, each introducing multiple variables that affect water quality depending on the site configuration. Accordingly, the German regulation classifies stormwater based on its pollutant load using the TSS 63 parameter, which differentiates between three categories: low, moderate, and high (DWA, 2007).

To establish a reference site, it has been defined that the technologies analyzed will serve a residential environment, where the drained areas include roofs, low-traffic roads, and parking lots. The values observed in case studies CS4a, CS4b, and CS5 are used to define water quality. The selected values are calculated as an average of the concentrations recorded in the three systems to obtain a single representative concentration. The selected values are presented in Table A 5.

Although some values are higher and exceed the ranges indicated by GÖBEL et al. (2007), they have been adopted after consultation with an expert in water management and LCA in order to have a more accurate representation of the actual system conditions (RHEMY, C., 20.12.2024).

3.2 Life cycle assessment approach

The environmental assessment of technologies is performed through a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), a standardized methodology developed to assess the impacts related to the entire life cycle of a product, service, or technology. The assessment focuses on the production, use, and disposal phases of the life cycle, from cradle to grave. LCA uses multiple databases and software tools to model processes and material and energy flows. The methodology is internationally standardized under ISO 14040 and ISO 14044, which define the four main phases for its application: Goal and scope Definition, Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), and Interpretation of the results (ISO 14040, 2006; ISO 14044, 2006). The present work is structured and developed according to the phases indicated.

The goal and scope definition phase establishes the purpose of the study, delimiting the boundaries of the system and the quality of the data used. In this section, the functional unit

(FU) is also defined, which represents the function of the system under analysis and provides the basis for data collection and comparison.

LCI involves collecting and organizing data. During this phase, the allocation is performed, whereby the input and output flows are distributed among the different processes of the system. The data sources and assumptions used in the modeling are also specified.

The LCIA phase translates the data collected in the inventory into environmental impacts, applying specific characterization factors for each process or material within the defined impact categories.

Finally, the interpretation of the results allows the identification of the processes with the most significant impact on the system, evaluating the reliability and consistency of the data, and formulating strategies to reduce the environmental impact.

A common methodological framework is established and applied to all cases before conducting the individual LCA analyses for each technology group. Although each group differs in terms of treated water type, quality, and system boundaries, the overall LCA approach remains the same. The following sections provide a general overview of the key aspects of each phase for all groups before elaborating on the specific characteristics of each technology.

3.3 Goal and scope

3.3.1 Goal definition

The goal of this study is to assess and compare the environmental performance of different runoff and CSO treatment technologies that are part of the StopUP project, which aims to provide innovative solutions for the sustainable management of water resources. Some technologies are still in the pilot phase, meaning that the inventories and design parameters are subject to higher uncertainty. The results achieved, however, are expected to guide decision-making on the choice of materials and construction processes and provide insight into the environmental implications of the technologies over a 30-year lifetime.

The project partners and other actors interested in implementing sustainable urban drainage solutions are the target stakeholders. Initially, the analysis is helpful for internal decision-making and the eventual optimization of prototypes prior to large-scale implementation. Subsequently, in case the results are of interest for publication, it is necessary to comply with the critical review requirements stipulated in the ISO 14044 standard due to the comparative nature of the analysis.

3.3.2 Scope definition

The scope of the study includes key elements. It describes the functional unit, system boundaries, and life cycle phases. It also describes data collection, impact assessment methodology, assumptions, and limitations. Each of these aspects is described below.

Functional unit

The function of the systems is to control and treat combined CSO and runoff, reducing the discharge of pollutants into receiving water bodies. The first functional unit refers to the total volume treated in 30 years. The volumes covered by each case study are provided in Table C 16 and Table C 17.

Three groups of technologies are defined, all of which fulfil similar treatment functions but under different operational conditions. Due to the variation in pollutant loads across the treated waters, a direct comparison between all case studies is not appropriate. Technologies designed for heavily polluted CSO treatment cannot be directly compared with those intended for runoff treatment, as their target pollutant loads and treatment requirements differ significantly. To account for these differences, additional FUs for the three groups of technologies are defined as follows:

- Group 1: Treatment of 1 m³ of CSO under mean influent concentrations, as presented in Table A 3.
- Group 2: Treatment of 1 m³ of CSO under peak influent concentrations, as presented in Table A 3.
- Group 3: Treatment of 1 m³ of runoff according to the concentrations in Table A 5.

Data collection and quality

The inventory data originates from primary and secondary sources. Primary data were obtained through bilateral communications with the partners involved in the StopUP project, who contributed expertise on technology performance, material use, and operating parameters. When primary data was not available, secondary sources from literature and technical databases were used to complement the analysis, especially in the case of innovative materials such as chitosan, MS13X zeolite, and Sorbacid, which lack representative entries in LCA databases. In these cases, estimates were derived and adjusted to the scale and context of each case study.

Data collection also includes the design assumptions for each technology. Expert judgment and extrapolations from laboratory-scale data were applied when direct measurements were limited. To ensure consistency across the assessment, all technologies are modelled under a

European context, aligning with inventory flows labelled “RER” (Europe) where available, or “GLO” (global) when specific European data were not accessible.

Impact assessment methodology

The modeling is carried out with the OpenLCA v2.2 software. For the elaboration of inventories and the collection of reference processes, the ecoinvent v3.10 database is used. Environmental impacts are evaluated using the ReCiPe 2016 v1.03 (Hierarchist perspective) methodology (HUIJBREGTS et al., 2017). The analysis is focused on the midpoint categories: climate change, acidification potential, freshwater eutrophication, marine eutrophication, freshwater ecotoxicity, marine ecotoxicity, and water use.

Assumptions and limitations

The following assumptions have been made to provide consistency and address data limitations:

Precipitation variability: A constant annual precipitation is assumed for 30 years without accounting for rainfall variations or storm intensity. Hydrological studies are not included in the scope of this research.

Materials: Inventory data for innovative adsorbents or flocculants were obtained from literature studies. Extrapolated values may produce uncertainty, which should be considered when interpreting the comparative results.

Transportation: The distances are based on literature values and the experience of the ATD team in construction projects. Adjustments have been made to reflect current availability and logistical operations, including 50 km for concrete, 150 km for reinforced concrete components, and 50 km for excavated soil. Standard transport distances are listed in Appendix B, Table B 1. Specific materials for particular systems are assessed individually, with details given in the relevant inventories. The assumed mode of transport is 32-ton trucks.

Component replacement: For systems that require mechanical components such as pumps and mixers for their operation, it is assumed that these parts will need to be replaced once during their lifetime.

End-of-Life: A decommissioning scenario has not been modeled due to uncertainty about future disposal or recovery options. Only waste generated during operations is taken into account.

Cut-off Method: Following a cut-off approach, any potential secondary use or recycling benefit of the recovered materials is allocated to the recycling system. Consequently, the original system receives no credit for resource recovery. This applies specifically to the processing of

organic waste generated in vegetative systems. In this case, environmental impacts are accounted for only up to the point of handover to the processing facility, which is assumed to be composting.

Data Exclusions: Processes common to all case studies and scenarios, such as fixed transport distances for maintenance personnel, are excluded from the comparison. All systems are assumed to require maintenance once every four months, with a fixed transport distance of ten kilometers for personnel. This exclusion does not extend to transportation related to component replacement, waste disposal, or other operational inputs, which are accounted for separately.

Additional benefits, such as aesthetic value, increased groundwater infiltration, plant evapotranspiration, and microbial uptake, are not considered in the operation phase.

Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis accounts for possible variations in the energy mix, transportation distances, and water quality parameters that influence the overall results. For instance, if the electricity grid mix becomes less carbon-intensive over the next 30 years, processes that consume a significant amount of energy could have a lower environmental impact. These analyses will be presented in the final interpretation section.

3.3.3 System Boundaries

The system boundaries follow a “cradle-to-operation” approach, with partial consideration of the end-of-life. The construction phase encompasses the following processes:

- Production and manufacturing of materials: Extraction of raw materials, production processes, and manufacturing of components used in technologies.
- Transport of materials to the installation site: The distances and transportation modes are based on reference values reported in the literature and adjusted where necessary to provide more representative conditions.
- Excavation and earthworks: Includes only excavation activities, excluding site preparation, foundation work, soil stabilization, waste management, and the temporary water and electricity supply.

The operation phase includes energy use, operational inputs, component replacements, and generation of residues (e.g., used filter bags and sorbents). The performance of the system is calculated by the total amount of contaminants retained. The analysis is based on removal efficiencies, considering a 30-year lifetime and using experimental data provided by the partners. The results are relevant for contaminants, including total suspended solids (TSS), phosphorus (P), nitrogen (N), and heavy metals, allowing an assessment of the relative benefit

of each technology compared to the no-intervention scenario. In this context, effluent discharges are classified as point source emissions (PSE), following the definition of BRUDLER (2019), and are referred to as such throughout this study. To provide a comprehensive assessment, the results distinguish between three impact components: those associated with the construction phase, the operation phase, and point source emissions. The system boundaries for each technology are indicated below.

Baseline scenarios

It covers the evaluation of reference scenarios, including the scenario without intervention (scenario a), the scenario with WWTP operation (scenario b), and the conventional solution with a storage tank (scenario c). The system boundaries for these reference scenarios are illustrated for each case study in the corresponding figures.

In the No Intervention scenario, the system boundary considers only the CSO and its associated water quality parameters, representing both the inflow and untreated outflow discharged directly into surface waters. In the WWTP operation scenario, it is assumed that the system can treat the additional water generated in the catchment area without exceeding the treatment capacity. The system boundary includes treating the wet weather flow, accounting for energy consumption, and using flocculants to achieve standard effluent quality. Once treated, the water is discharged to the surface water. Sludge formation due to increased organic load and biomass growth is excluded from the boundary. Studies highlight that the environmental impacts of sludge treatment can vary significantly depending on the method used and the specific process condition (PRADEL et al., 2019). Therefore, quantifying benefits or impacts is outside the scope of the analysis, as it unnecessarily introduces uncertainties. Although sludge treatment may require intensive processing, it can also provide benefits, such as energy recovery through biogas production. Thus, this process is considered neutral within the limits.

Emissions generated by biological processes during wastewater treatment, such as methane or nitrous oxide, are also excluded. These emissions are not considered as, in the absence of treatment, the same biological processes would occur naturally in the receiving water bodies (MARESCAUX et al., 2018), making them redundant for this analysis.

Scenario C is an extension of the WWTP operation system. It incorporates a storage tank designed to buffer the wet weather flow before it is directed to WWTP for treatment. Both the construction and operational phases of the storage tank are included within the system boundaries.

In scenarios B and C in combined systems, the influent water technically corresponds to the wet weather flow. However, this study assumes that the wet weather flow is equivalent to the

CSO to ensure comparability with the technologies that manage CSO volumes. Based on this assumption, the wet weather flow and CSO have equivalent characteristics and pollutant concentrations. Thus, throughout the analysis, the influent water in all scenarios will be referred to as CSO volume.

Detailed illustrations of the system boundaries for scenarios b and c are provided in Appendix B, Figure B 1 to Figure B 3. The following sections focus on the specific scenarios and configurations associated with each technology

Combined sewer overflow treatment systems for mean concentrations

CS1: Retention soil filter

The Compact RSF (CS1e and f) is a modified version of the traditional RSF design (CS1d), specifically developed to reduce the physical footprint of the system while preserving the treatment performance of the original configuration. This enhanced design integrates in-channel bioflocculant dosing, which improves the aggregation and removal of suspended solids, resulting in a simplified and more efficient system layout. Scenarios CS1e and CS1f differ in the configuration of the external containment: CS1e utilizes concrete walls, while CS1f employs soil embankments. Figure 3.4 provides an overview of the system boundaries for these scenarios, including resource inputs and outputs. The “as-built” RSF (CS1d) system boundaries are further detailed in Appendix B, Figure B 4 and Figure B 5. The following section focuses on the compact RSF (CS1e and f).

The system boundary for the construction phase of the Compact RSF, as depicted in Figure 3.5, focuses on the main processes contributing to environmental impacts. The system includes raw material extraction and processing, which uses of resources such as sand, gravel, calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), concrete, steel, geotextiles, HDPE- pipes, and tanks. Logistics and transportation of raw materials from production sites to the construction site are also included. However, equipment and personnel transportation are excluded.

Excavation activities include excavation and transporting excavated material to disposal or reuse sites. However, disposal or reuse operations of excavated material are excluded from the system boundary. Also excluded are on-site construction processes such as soil mixing, grading, vegetation planting, irrigation, and fertilization. These processes are considered insignificant in terms of their material and energy inputs relative to the system as a whole.

Figure 3.4: System boundary and scenarios for case study 1

Figure 3.6 presents the system boundary for the compact RSF operating phase. The untreated CSO inflow, estimated at 900,000 m³ per year, enters the system carrying suspended solids, nutrients, and heavy metals. The treated effluent is assumed to achieve a 100% discharge rate to surface waters.

A distinctive aspect of the Compact RSF system is the integration of biofloculant-related processes, which include producing and transporting biofloculant materials and their dosing and management within the system. Pumping operations are performed for biofloculant dosing and channel emptying after a CSO event.

The system integrates vegetation, specifically *Phragmites australis* (common reed), which requires neither mowing nor removal. As PINNEKAMP (2017) emphasizes, the natural biomass of this vegetation actively contributes to the functioning of the system. The decomposition of plant material forms a layer that favors the development of a structurally rich filter surface, preventing clogging. These natural processes support the ecological nature of the Compact RSF system, eliminating the regular maintenance of vegetation and the consequent disposal of organic debris. The potential for carbon dioxide (CO₂) sequestration by vegetation is excluded from this study, as the amount absorbed is minimal and does not significantly offset environmental impacts from material and energy demands (VAN DEN BERG et al., 2016).

Figure 3.5: System boundary for the construction phase of the Compact RSF

Figure 3.6: System boundary for the operation phase of the Compact RSF

CS3: Wastewater treatment plant smart management

The smart WWTP management uses advanced control software to optimize its operation. Case Study 3 (Scenario b) refers to a system with an existing wastewater treatment plant (WWTP), which has increased its treatment capacity through operational adjustments rather than additional civil works. The different scenarios, CS3a no intervention, CS3b smart management, and CS3c implementation of the storage tank with WWTP operation, are shown in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7: System boundary and scenarios for case study 3

Population growth and the connection of additional areas in the sewer system lead to a significant increase in combined sewer overflow (CSO) volumes. Weather forecasting tools and control software are used to optimize treatment processes several hours in advance in case of rainfall to address this challenge.

The Birs WWTP illustrates how this adaptation can be carried out without additional infrastructure, taking advantage of radar data and control algorithms. These modifications have enabled the WWTP to treat 875,000 m³ more water per year, representing an increase of 7.3% over its operational capacity before implementing the control system. The plant operation requires inputs such as flocculants and energy consumption.

Although the shortening of some treatment stages may lead to a slight reduction in efficiency, especially in nitrogen removal, the partners ensure that the final effluent quality remains within the established regulatory parameters and that there is no major difference in effluent values other than in the dry weather operation of the plant.

The inventory of the radar system has been excluded from the analysis, as third parties manage it, and its signal transmission to the plant does not significantly contribute to the environmental impact. In addition, the computer system used for process optimization already existed prior to the implementation of the controller and, therefore, does not introduce a new impact factor at the construction level. Figure 3.8 shows the system boundary for the operational phase. All the considerations outlined in baseline scenario c are applicable in this case.

Figure 3.8: System boundary for the operation phase of the WWTP smart management

CS6: Improved constructed wetlands

Among the case studies analyzed is the improved constructed wetland. This system is evaluated comparatively against the previously defined baseline scenarios, whose system boundaries are illustrated in Figure 3.9. It shows the CSO flow, the main components of each alternative, and the discharge routes to the receiving environment.

The improved constructed wetland has three essential components for operation. It first features physical pretreatment, designed to promote solids settling and prevent clogging in the later stages of treatment. The water is then processed in two constructed wetlands arranged in series.

Pretreatment consists of a subsurface reinforced concrete tank equipped with a low-power pump to transfer the CSO flow to the wetlands. It also has a cast iron manhole and stainless-steel steps to facilitate access, maintenance, and emptying of the tank. Both wetlands have PVC piping, gravel as filter media, geotextile, and pond liners. In addition, two reinforced concrete control structures are included, one at the outlet of each wetland. During the construction phase, the materials described above are included, as well as the excavation work necessary to remove the soil and enable both the filter and the sedimentation tank. The system boundaries for the construction phase are depicted in Figure B 6.

Figure 3.9: System boundary and scenarios for case study 6

Figure 3.10: System boundary for the operation phase of the improved constructed wetland

The treatment system can handle 500 m³ of water per day, considering an average of 32 rainfall events per year. The filter system incorporates common reeds (*Phragmites australis*). However, carbon capture by these plants is not considered, as it is assumed to be limited to offset the environmental impact of the constructed wetland (VAN DEN BERG et al., 2016). The life span of the wetlands is estimated at 30 years. Given the limited number of annual events, it is assumed that replacing the filter media will not be necessary, as it would require continuous use, for example, treating domestic wastewater, which does not apply in this context. Energy consumption is mainly associated with pumping the flow and vegetation maintenance during operation. The system generates organic vegetation waste, which is transported to a green waste facility for further processing. However, following the cut-off principle for impact

allocation, only the transport of biomass to the treatment facility is considered within the system boundaries. Processes such as sludge treatment and transportation of equipment and personnel are excluded. Figure 3.10 illustrates the key processes in the operational phase, highlighting their interactions as a basis for the impact assessment.

Combined sewer overflow treatment systems for peak concentrations

CS2: Filtration-adsorption system

Two scenarios are evaluated within the limits of the filtration-adsorption system. Although both scenarios share the same structure of the filtration-adsorption, the desorption process differs, especially regarding the amount and handling of the regenerant solution. In the first scenario, the regenerant solution is reused, with small additions of fresh regenerant before being completely replaced after several cycles.

In the second scenario, the regenerant solution is used once and then disposed of, therefore needing to be replaced in high volumes in each cycle. Figure 3.11 illustrates the compared scenarios, including the baselines cases described above. In this case, the storage tank scenario has been modelled to accommodate the conditions specific to the system.

During the construction phase of the system, a variety of materials are required to ensure the functionality of its structural and operational components. Reinforced concrete is used for the foundation and the storage tank, stainless steel for the adsorption and desorption columns, and PVC-U for the housing of the filter bags. Adsorption materials, including zeolites (MS13X) and Sorbacid 911, are incorporated alongside regenerant solutions based on NaCl and Na₂CO₃. The system also includes electronic devices and mechanical components, such as pumps and sensors. The construction phase is identical in scenarios CS2c and CS2d, regardless of the inclusion or absence of regenerant solution recycling. The system accounts for only 5% of the total impacts associated with the construction of the desorption unit, as it is assumed that multiple decentralized filtration-adsorption systems are implemented throughout the sewer network. Consequently, the construction of the desorption plant is distributed among these individual filtration-adsorption systems, leading to an allocation of the inventory data. Figure B 7 provides a detailed overview of all the flows and processes involved in this phase.

The operational phase includes all the processes required to treat 15,000 m³/year of CSO, as depicted in Figure 3.12. The system boundaries include the filtration, adsorption, and desorption processes along with material flows, energy consumption, and emissions associated with transport and operation.

Figure 3.11: System boundary and scenarios for case study 2

The main operational activities involve the periodic replacement of filter bags, the use of adsorbents such as MS13X zeolites and Sorbacid 911, and the regeneration of these adsorbents using NaCl and Na₂CO₃ solutions. The desorption process considers two scenarios where the regenerant solution is either recycled over several cycles before its final disposal or discarded after a single use. Although the goal of the system is the recovery of ammonium and phosphorus, this analysis does not include the additional steps required for complete recovery. Research has not yet advanced enough to evaluate all alternatives for the recovery and reuse of these products. Consequently, further treatment and recovery of phosphates and ammonium remain outside the scope of this study.

The operation phase also includes waste management, specifically the final disposal of filter bags, which are assumed to be treated as a plastic waste mixture through municipal incineration. However, the transport and treatment of suspended solids captured during filtration at WWTP are not included.

Figure 3.12: System boundary for the operation phase of the Filtration-Adsorption system

Urban runoff treatment systems

The system boundaries for the runoff treatment technologies include all relevant life cycle stages, material production, construction and operation. Figure 3.13 illustrates the boundaries and scenarios for case studies CS4a, CS4b and CS5, detailing the flow of runoff through each treatment system. The figure also includes reference scenarios (CS0a, CS0b and CS0c), which serve as benchmarks for evaluating the environmental performance of the adopted technologies.

Figure 3.13: System boundaries and scenarios for case studies CS4a, CS4b and CS5

For the SuDS, the entire volume of treated water is assumed to be infiltrated into the subsurface. The analysis includes material inputs, energy consumption, waste generation during operation, and the avoided environmental impacts of pollutant retention within the system.

Within the StopUP project, water quality monitoring is contemplated for all the technologies through periodic analysis of parameters such as turbidity, pH, and concentration of contaminants. However, this monitoring is excluded from the limits of the study due to the lack of concrete data on the frequency and transport conditions of the personnel. It is assumed that, in all systems, these sampling tasks are carried out with the same methodology, frequency, and travel distance so that their contribution does not differentially alter the comparative analysis.

CS4a: Gravel and sand filter

The gravel and sand filter construction considers the excavation necessary to install the sedimentation basin, filter, and swale. The main construction components include bentonite mats to waterproof the basin and gravel, sand, pebbles, geotextile, and a pond liner for the filter. In addition, HDPE distribution channels and a reinforced concrete retaining wall are incorporated to direct and support the flow.

Initially, the design incorporated other activities, such as removing trees and shrubs and building pathways and playgrounds. However, these elements have been excluded to simplify the comparison and focus the analysis on the primary filtering function, as they represent landscape and recreational amenities that do not impact runoff treatment efficiency. Figure B 8 illustrates the materials included in the filter construction inventory.

Figure 3.14 illustrates the main activities planned for the operational phase of the system, including the replacement of the filter media and the periodic maintenance of the swale, which involves trimming the vegetation on its surface. These tasks are carried out using electric equipment, representing the primary energy consumption during this phase. Additionally, a cut-off principle is applied to the extracted biomass, which is transported to a composting facility without assigning it any subsequent environmental benefits or burdens. The vegetation cover on the swale is considered minimal, and therefore, its potential contribution to carbon sequestration is assumed negligible.

Moreover, the management of sludge generated in the sedimentation basin is not included in this analysis due to the lack of precise information on the amount accumulated and the frequency of removal. It is important to note that, since this is a gravity flow system, no pumps are required to transport water from the basin to the filter or from the filter to the swale, which helps to minimize both the operating costs and energy consumption of the process.

Figure 3.14: System boundary for the operation phase of the gravel and sand filter

CS4b: Urban Rain Shell

The construction of the URS is depicted in Figure B 9. The sedimentation tank, located upstream of the filter, is constructed of concrete, reinforcing steel and cast iron. The filtration system incorporates AA shells and AA minerals, complemented by a geotextile membrane. The distribution piping system consists of PVC and HDPE pipes.

Detailed inventories of AA shells and AA minerals are not publicly available due to patents. However, to account for their environmental footprint, characterization factors have been derived from previous studies on the sustainability of these materials and incorporated into the system boundaries.

The shell filter requires minimal maintenance during its operational phase, with no significant processes to be considered within the system boundary (Figure 3.15). The exclusion of sludge management corresponds to the same consideration applied to the sand filter, as there is insufficient data available on the amount of sludge accumulated in the tank. Therefore, in order to avoid introducing additional uncertainty in the analysis, this aspect has been omitted. However, overall system efficiency in removing total suspended solids (TSS) has been quantified and provided by the project partners.

In addition, the filter media does not require replacement over the lifetime of the system. Its long-term performance and media degradation were considered in the design phase, ensuring that the necessary amount of shells and minerals are incorporated from the initial stage to maintain treatment efficacy over time.

Figure 3.15: System boundary for the operation phase of URS filter

CS5: Bioretention cell

The system boundaries encompass both the construction and operation phases. During the construction phase (Figure B 10), the system includes procurement of raw materials, processing of individual components, transportation from production facilities to the construction site and excavation. Materials considered in the system include mulch, engineered soil, gravel for the drainage area and pipes for the drainage system to manage overflow. In addition, a geotextile layer is included to increase the stability of the system.

However, certain activities are excluded, such as soil mixing, land leveling, vegetation planting and irrigation until plants are established. Also not included within the limits are the transport of equipment and personnel to the site or any process beyond the transport of the excavated material to its disposal or reuse.

Figure 3.16 details the processes included in the operational phase. In this phase, the bioretention cell requires maintenance on a regular basis. Although maintenance is essential to avoid loss of efficiency (BHATT et al., 2019), it has been simplified to general procedures, which include pruning, weeding, and transporting vegetation and organic waste to a composting facility. This assumption is necessary due to the lack of detailed data on specific maintenance practices.

As for the topsoil, mulch is expected to decompose over the lifetime of the system (NOWAK et al., 2002). However, since it also contributes to the adsorption capacity of the treatment process, it is expected to be replaced once during this period. Vegetative effects of the bioretention cell, including carbon sequestration, are not considered as previous research suggests that a BRC without trees has a negligible impact on the overall footprint (BHATT et al., 2019).

The operational lifespan of the system has been estimated at 30 years based on recommendations from the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) project partner. Consequently, no filter media replacement is foreseen.

Figure 3.16: System boundary for the operational phase of the BRC

3.4 Life cycle inventory

The life cycle inventory analysis compiles information on the mass and energy flows within the system boundaries currently defined for each technology. The data collection process was based on technical drawings, material specifications, and discussions with the researchers responsible for each case study. Since some technologies are still in early development, direct measurements and comprehensive datasets were not always available. Consequently, several assumptions were made, drawing upon existing literature, best practices in stormwater treatment systems, and, where necessary, manufacturer specifications on materials, processes, and commercially available solutions.

The following section presents the assumptions made for the construction and operational phases of each technology. The construction phase is classified into excavation and earthwork, structural materials, plastic materials, and natural and composite materials, while the operation phase, which is presented for a useful life of 30 years, is classified into operational inputs, replacement components, energy consumption, and waste management, accounting for all materials required over this period.

The inventory of material and energy inputs for the construction and operational phases is provided in the appendix of each case study. A breakdown of these inputs is presented in Appendix C, where section C 1. presents the life cycle inventory for material and energy requirements, and section C 2. provides an overview of influent and effluent water quality parameters, along with the removal efficiencies of the treatment technologies.

3.4.1 Assumptions for baseline scenarios

Scenario b: WWTP operation

The operation of the WWTP is modeled based on two main flows: operational inputs and energy consumption. The operational inputs include the flocculant. Energy consumption is determined by the electricity required for the treatment processes. The total amount of these components is documented in the inventories for each case within scenario b.

The flocculant used in the WWTP is iron (III) chloride (FeCl_3) in a 40% solution sourced from the ecoinvent database. The required dose was determined stoichiometrically, assuming complete precipitation of phosphorus as FePO_4 . The flocculant dosage is adjusted according to the influent phosphorus concentration in each case study.

- CS1, CS3, and CS6: 7.8 mg/L for a phosphorus concentration of 1.5 mg/L.
- CS2: 26.16 mg/L for a phosphorus concentration of 5 mg/L.
- CS4a, CS4b and CS5: 1.57 mg/L for a phosphorus concentration of 0.3 mg/L.

The specific electricity consumption for the WWTP treatment process is 0.27 kWh/m^3 . This value was calculated from the specific average inlet water volume reported by BINGGELI et al. (2023), which considers an average value of 322 L per population equivalent per day, including stormwater inputs. In addition, the energy demand per population equivalent, set at 32 kWh/E^*a for size class 5, follows the values reported by FRICKE (2009).

The removal efficiencies applied are based on WWTP performance values, with adjustments to account for dilution effects. The adjusted values are presented in Table C 16 in the Appendix.

Scenario c: Storage tank and WWTP operation

Each technology analyzed is directly compared to a conventional solution, with the storage tank serving as the reference system. Its construction consists of reinforced concrete walls, requiring excavation for implementation, and incorporates stainless steel components, such as beams and internal ladders. The piping network is assumed to be made of high-density polyethylene.

For CSO treatment technologies, the tank is separated into multiple chambers, simulating a CSO storage facility that temporarily retains excess water prior to gradual discharge to the WWTP. For urban runoff technologies, the storage tank is entirely underground. Due to the smaller volume to be treated, there is no need for internal chambers. Nevertheless, a material allowance has been considered to include structural beams.

For systems with a storage capacity greater than 30,000 m³, the dimensions were based on the storage tank constructed at the Aachen WWTP, maintaining the length and height while adjusting the width. For systems with a lower capacity, the dimensions were modified accordingly to adapt to the required storage volume. The wall thickness was set at 35 cm and the base thickness at 40 cm. In addition, technical drawings provided by FHNW were used to complete and further develop the design.

To maintain comparability between the storage tank and the technologies, the tank size was adjusted to the maximum design volume of each system. Thus, all study scenarios support equivalent hydraulic loads.

Structural materials: Structural materials: According to the reinforcement weights per cubic meter of concrete indicated by UGOCHUKWU et al. (2020), a composition of 98% concrete and 2% steel was assumed, which corresponds to approximately 150 kg of steel per cubic meter of concrete. This proportion corresponds to the concrete properties required in wet conditions, where adequate resistance to cracking is desired. A 15% increase in both concrete and steel was included to account for additional structural elements such as inlet and outlet channels, support beams and access platforms. In addition, the infrastructure incorporates 50 MPa concrete with CEM II/B cement.

Pumping electricity: The energy consumption required to pump the water flow from the tank to the treatment plant is calculated as a function of the average dynamic head and not the total head since the water level in the tank fluctuates during operation. An average head equal to half the maximum total head reflects this variation (THOMANN, M., 30.01.2025). A margin of 15% is also included to consider friction losses in pipes, elbows, and valves throughout the system. The specific energy consumption of each storage tank is detailed in Table A 7 in the appendix.

Electrical and control systems: The estimates are based on the technical drawings of the Birs WWTP storage tank and have been scaled to the dimensions of each system (see Table B 2 in the appendix). Wiring lengths are adjusted to the length, width, and height within each system. Stainless steel is assumed for the grounding ring, with a length corresponding to the perimeter, and for the equipotential bonding, with a length equivalent to the width.

Piping: The piping system is dimensioned similarly to the electrical and control system. Detailed specifications are given in Table B 3 of the appendix.

3.4.2 Assumptions for case study 1

CS1d: RSF “as-built”

The system is fully implemented, and the inventory was established based on the material specifications used in its construction. ATD provided the data for this scenario. However, certain assumptions were necessary to complete the dataset. First, it is assumed that all excavated soil is transported off-site, with no reuse at the project location. Additionally, the analysis considers only the transportation of plants, excluding the cultivation process and any related agricultural activities from the system boundaries.

Several assumptions were made for the operational phase of the system. A fertilizer application is not considered, as it is not part of the typical maintenance procedures for this system.

The assessment of energy consumption in the RSF system focuses exclusively on the operation of the two pumps used to evacuate the remaining stormwater, 2,000 m³ per rainfall event. The drainage process begins when the water percolates through the filter bed. However, this natural drainage is limited by the elevation of the concrete weirs located along the distribution channels since once the water reaches this elevation, it cannot be evacuated by gravity alone. A pumping system is necessary to evacuate this residual volume and convey it to WWTP.

Compact Retention Soil Filter

The compact RSF introduces design modifications by reducing the filter area by half, from 14,600 m² to 7,300 m². The distribution channels, originally designed to serve six compartments, have been reconfigured to serve three. However, this reduction in area is not translated proportionally to all other system components, as several structural elements remain unchanged, are modified or are omitted.

The inlet channels retain the same configuration as in the original system. At the same time, the central dividing structure, which previously separated the filter into two sections, now functions as an external structural element. The total footprint of the system changes depending on the selected configuration, determined by the outer perimeter built with reinforced concrete walls or embankments. The footprint is reduced in the concrete wall configuration, but this design requires a larger volume of concrete. On the contrary, in the embankment configuration, although the total occupied area does not exceed that of the original system, it is greater than the area previously occupied by the embankments being replaced.

The reduction in surface area results mainly in less filter material. However, it does not imply a proportional reduction in the use of concrete. The concrete that would have been saved by

eliminating the three compartments is instead used to increase the height of the central dividing structures.

CS1e: Compact retention soil filter (concrete wall)

The first configuration involves replacing embankments with 500 mm thick reinforced concrete walls designed to withstand the increased hydraulic pressure resulting from the higher water column. The compact system operates with a containment height of 5.5 m, requiring a structurally reinforced perimeter of 245 meters.

The excavated volume is calculated as half the original filter area multiplied by the new height plus the volume occupied by the external concrete retaining wall.

The total concrete volume remains unchanged from CS1d, as the reduction in footprint is offset by the increased height, resulting in no overall material savings. The structural components that remain in the system but are extended in height are modeled with 35 MPa concrete and CEM II/A cement. The new external retaining wall is modeled using 50 MPa concrete and CEM II/B cement.

High-density polyethylene pipes (HDPE) and geotextile are estimated to be 50 % of the quantity used in CS1d. The pond liner consumption is reduced by slightly less than fifty percent compared to the original configuration, as it excludes the material covering the embankment, which is calculated arithmetically based on the embankment surface area. Additionally, two HDPE storage tanks with a total capacity of forty cubic meters are included for biofloculant storage, which is a sufficient supply for four precipitation events.

The metal works follow the original system design, with stainless steel components for stairs and handrails, which are modeled for the remaining sections of the system corresponding to the three filter compartments. The use of galvanized steel is reduced by 50 %. The electrical and control systems also undergo modifications, with the wiring, grounding ring, and equipotential bonding system reduced by 50 %.

Regarding the mechanical components, a pump with a flow rate of three liters per second and a total head of one meter is integrated for biofloculant dosing. Additionally, a stirrer is incorporated for biofloculant mixing, with an electricity consumption of 0.19 Wh per cubic meter of treated water.

Operational inputs include the dosing of the biofloculant. According to the supplier, the solution consists of 2% chitosan and 1% acetic acid by mass (WUNDER, A., 16.12.2024). The optimum dosage for effective treatment is 5 mg chitosan per liter of wastewater, which is equivalent to a supply of the solution of 0.25 liters per cubic meter of wastewater (STORATH, J.,

11.11.2024). Details of the inventory of the biofloculant solution are given in Table C 31 in the Appendix.

Currently, no LCA is available for the chitosan intended to be used for the technology (WUNDER, A., 16.12.2024). Specific flows to assess the environmental impact of chitosan are not available in the ecoinvent database. Therefore, values reported in the literature were used, referring to LCA studies conducted by BASHIRI et al. (2025) and RIOFRIO et al. (2021). It should be noted that these impacts may vary depending on the type of processes, the selected flows, and the geographic region where the transformation occurs. Additionally, the environmental impacts associated with the use of acetic acid and water were incorporated into the total chitosan impacts to model the complete solution provided by the supplier. The transport distance is 580 km, corresponding to the distance from the RSF location to the supplier in Landsberg, Germany.

The operational phase also includes the energy consumption of the pumps required for draining the distribution and inlet channels. In this configuration, the volume to be evacuated is assumed to be half of that in the as-built system, resulting in 1,000 cubic meters.

The treatment efficiencies are based on studies conducted by FRECHEN (2013), GROTEHUSMANN and KASTING (2008), and PINNEKAMP (2017). The research team responsible for the Compact RSF configuration indicated that its treatment efficiency is equivalent to the As-built RSF configuration. Consequently, a single efficiency value has been applied to both scenarios.

CS1f: Compact retention soil filter (embankment)

The second configuration includes the embankments; however, as the system height increases, their size expands accordingly to maintain structural stability.

The total concrete volume of structural materials remains unchanged from the as-built scenario. For plastic materials, the geotextile requirements are equivalent to those in CS1e, with additional material incorporated to cover the lateral surface of the embankments. All other assumptions remain consistent with those previously established for CS1e.

3.4.3 Assumptions for case study 2

UNIBO provided a detailed technical layout of the plant components, which served as the basis for inventory development. The layout incorporated the materials for the filtration, adsorption, and desorption processes. Following the layout, assumptions were made regarding the materials for the structural components.

For the desorption unit, the assumptions were initially based on the total material quantities to reflect the complete system construction accurately. However, in line with the defined system boundaries, the inventory presented in Table C 7 accounts for only 5% of the total material input, considering a potential future installation of 20 decentralized filtration-adsorption plants. The specific assumptions applied to the systems are detailed below.

The storage tank is the only component that requires soil excavation, as it is installed below ground level. The excavation volume is equivalent to the total volume occupied by the tank.

For the structural components, the retention tank walls were assumed to have a thickness of 15 cm, with a total volume of 98 m³ and a surface area of 19 m². Concrete and reinforcing steel were also incorporated into the foundation of the filtration-adsorption plant and the desorption unit, with an assumed thickness of 20 cm. The total footprint of both systems amounts to 616 m², distributed as 56 m² for the compact system and 560 m² for the desorption system. The reinforcing steel content was estimated at 120 kg per cubic meter of concrete, following the values found in the literature (UGOCHUKWU et al., 2020).

The inventory of plastic materials includes three main elements: pipes, filter housing, and filter bags:

- The pipe lengths were determined based on the structural layout and provided areas.
- The filter housing (PVC-U) consists of 20 filter columns, each weighing 20 kg, as the supplier specifies for the HXP-BF-1-2-B column model. Additionally, 1% silicone is assumed for the gaskets (EUROTROL).
- The polypropylene filter bags, size 2, Ø 17.78 cm × 81.28 cm, are assumed to weigh 205 g. For both filter types, this value results from a filter area of 0.41 m² per bag and an area weight of 500 g/m² (FILMEDIA HOME, 21.09.2024). One bag can retain up to 25 kg of TSS. Given that the system removes 5,950 kg of TSS annually, this results in a replacement of 160 filter units per year.

The suppliers had no inventory specifications for either MS13X zeolite or Sorbacid 911. Therefore, the inventory was developed using literature data and the following assumptions:

- MS13X zeolite was modeled using a life cycle inventory of a proxy zeolite based on the study by FAWER et al. (1998). According to the specifications provided by UNIBO, the material is imported from China, requiring 18,350 km of sea transport and another 300 km by truck.
- Sorbacid 911 was assumed to have a chemical composition of 50% magnesium oxide, 30% aluminum hydroxide, and 20% sodium hydroxide. The energy consumption for manufacturing was estimated at 15 MJ per kilogram. The material is supplied from Germany, with an assumed transport distance of 600 km.

- MS13X Zeolite and Sorbacid 911 can undergo up to 100 regeneration cycles. Over the system lifetime, MS13X is regenerated 39 times, while Sorbacid undergoes 35 regeneration cycles. The consumption rate of zeolite was estimated at 0.105 kg per cubic meter, while Sorbacid is consumed at a rate of 0.049 kg per cubic meter.
- The regeneration process involves using regeneration agents modelled withecoinvent database flows. Sodium chloride (NaCl) in powder form was selected as the regeneration agent for nitrogen desorption, while sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃), produced via the Solvay process, was used for phosphorus desorption.

The adsorption and desorption columns are made of stainless steel. The column walls are 10 mm thick, while the base and cover are 5 mm thick, meeting the technical specifications listed in (EUROTANKWORKS). A 10% allowance is added to the total material inventory for the structural beams.

The system includes four stainless steel columns for each adsorption step. The zeolite adsorption columns have a bed volume of 55.54 cubic meters, with a height of 1.7 m and a radius of 1.23 m, as specified by the research team. The Sorbacid adsorption columns use a similar structure, but with a height of 3 m and a radius of 1.23 m, providing a bed volume of 31.2 cubic meters.

The desorption stage consists of two columns per nutrient regeneration process. The solutions are stored in a primary tank and supplied to the adsorption columns. After the desorption process, the nutrient-enriched solution is transferred to a secondary tank of identical dimensions.

For the zeolite desorption, the system operates with an aqueous NaCl solution stored in a tank with a total volume of 833.04 cubic meters and a bed volume of 15 cubic meters. This tank has a height of 10.4 meters and a radius of 5.2 meters. In contrast, the Sorbacid regeneration process uses a Na₂CO₃ solution in a tank with a total volume of 1,248 cubic meters and a bed volume of 40 cubic meters. The tank is 12 meters high and has a radius of 6 meters.

The system includes electrical, control components, and mechanical elements essential for filtration, adsorption, and desorption processes. The wiring length was estimated at 10 meters per electronic device. For the mechanical components, the inventory was compiled based on existing literature and standardized Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs). The stirrer selection follows the specifications outlined by FARD and BARKDOLL (2021), with the Wilo-EMU TR 16.145-4/6 model chosen for the inventory. The valve inventory is based on the EPD for Butterfly Valves (EPD INTERNATIONAL AB, 2022).

The system includes eight electronic components in the filtration process and six in the desorption process. These components are modeled using the electronics production flow for control units available in ecoinvent.

UNIBO provided the energy consumption data:

- Pumping water to the filtration system requires 47 kWh.
- Stirrer operation consumes 0.3 kWh.
- Pumping water to the adsorption system is estimated at 26 kWh.
- Valve operation requires 0.045 kWh.
- Electronic devices consume 0.036 kWh.
- The power demand for desorbent pumping is 19.1 kWh for nitrogen desorption and 16.3 kWh for phosphorus desorption.

Operational inputs include the transport distance between the desorption and the filtration-adsorption systems, which is assumed to be at least 10 km. The consumption of regenerant salts varies depending on the regeneration scenario. CS2d requires 0.55 kg of NaCl per cubic meter for nitrogen desorption and 1.3 kg of Na₂CO₃ per cubic meter for phosphorus desorption. In contrast, CS2e results in higher salt demand, with 4.2 kg of NaCl per cubic meter of wastewater for nitrogen desorption and 10 kg of Na₂CO₃ per cubic meter for phosphorus desorption. Water consumption for the desorption process is also different between the two scenarios. While CS2e requires 168 liters per cubic meter of treated water, the CS2d scenario reduces water consumption to 18 liters per cubic meter due to the reuse of the regeneration solution.

Waste management accounts for the disposal of polypropylene filters, which are assumed to undergo incineration at a municipal waste treatment facility. A transportation distance of 15 km is considered to the disposal site.

3.4.4 Assumptions for case study 3

CS3b: Wastewater treatment plant smart management

For CS3b, wastewater treatment plant smart management, the research group at FHNW has indicated that the difference in effluent water quality between standard operation at 550 L/s and an increased capacity of 1,000 L/s annually is negligible. Given this consideration, the assumptions established for scenario b are also applied to CS3b (see 3.4.1).

No further operational modifications have been introduced for CS3c, as the storage tank followed by WWTP operation remains aligned with the inventory previously established for scenario c (see 3.4.1).

3.4.5 Assumptions for case study 4a

The life cycle inventory of the gravel and sand filter system was developed based on the inventory of the system in its full-scale configuration. Data from this reference system were used to define and scale the material and energy flows required for the revised configuration. The values presented for excavation, structural materials, plastic components, natural and composite materials, operational inputs, and waste management were adjusted to reflect the conditions of the system under analysis.

The excavation and earthwork phase consists of preparing the ground for the buffer, filter, and swale. To comply with the original design of the system, 80% of the excavated material was transported off-site, while the remaining 20% was reused.

Regarding structural materials, the overflow weir construction incorporates reinforced and unreinforced concrete for slabs and walls. An 8 m long precast retaining wall was selected to match the revised width of the filter. Since only the length of the wall was specified in the inventory, a width of 0.5 m and a height of 1 m were assumed. The structure consists of 99% concrete and 1% steel reinforcement, using 40 MPa concrete with CEM IV/B cement, which was chosen for its lower clinker content, contributing to reduced CO₂ emissions.

For plastic components, 138 m² of HDPE sheets are allocated for waterproofing containment walls, green areas, and surrounding the filter. Additionally, 87 m² of geotextiles are included to separate soil layers and improve drainage. The drainage system incorporates 19 meters of HDPE DN400 pipe and 2 meters of PVC DN150 pipe for monitoring points.

The natural and composite materials include both filter and buffer materials. A bentonite mat covering 535 m² is used for waterproofing the buffer. Due to the lack of detailed technical specifications, an inventory was created to estimate its environmental impact, as detailed in the Appendix Table C 27. The filter consists of 50 m³ of sand and 46.1 m³ of gravel, values that were scaled based on the original system.

The operation phase includes energy consumption and maintenance activities, particularly swale pruning, which is required periodically. For an area of 210.6 m², the estimated energy demand over 30 years is 37.91 kWh, based on equipment specifications outlined in the input data for CS6 (See 3.4.8).

Regarding replacement components, the filter material is expected to last 15 to 20 years, meaning that one full replacement is anticipated within the operational period.

Waste management considerations include vegetation waste generated from system maintenance, primarily lawn mowing. Based on estimates from HERTEL et al. (2015), 1.7 kg/m² of vegetation waste is produced annually. As this biological waste is composted, a cut-off

approach is applied, meaning that only impacts from the transportation to the disposal site are considered.

The selected waste management strategy for the filter sand involves landfilling as an inert material. The inventory accounts for the transportation of used sand to the landfill. A transportation distance of 15 km to the landfill is assumed for this disposal scenario.

3.4.6 Assumptions for case study 4b

The structural materials of the sedimentation tank include a 20 cm thick base, while the walls and top cover are 15 cm thick. The composition is 98% reinforced concrete and 2% steel reinforcement. For maintenance access, the tank has a 1 m diameter cast iron manhole and stainless-steel steps. The structure was modeled using 40 MPa concrete with CEM IV/B cement, selected for its lower clinker content to minimize CO₂ emissions. Detailed specifications and dimensions are given in Table A 10 of Appendix A.

As for the plastic components, the filter is fed by a DN400 PVC pipe, which is split into two DN200 HDPE pipes to facilitate infiltration within the liner layer. The system incorporates an aeration component consisting of a DN90 HDPE pipe along the entire length of the filter, with two vertical branches extending to the surface to allow air flow. A geotextile layer is placed between the soil and the shells (top layer) and between the minerals and the soil (bottom layer). In addition, a monitoring well with a DN150 PVC pipe is included.

3.4.7 Assumptions for case study 5

The BRC inventory was developed based on a series of assumptions regarding its construction, operation and maintenance phases. The aspects considered in the inventory include plastic components, natural and composite materials, substitute components, energy use and waste management.

The plastic components of the system include a DN1600 HDPE perforated pipe, functioning as an underdrain to convey excess water to the sewer system when the infiltration capacity of the soil is exceeded. A geotextile layer separates the engineered soil from the gravel layer to maintain drainage efficiency. A DN150 PVC pipe has also been integrated to monitor and sample the system.

The BRC includes vegetation, though, as in previous case studies, only the transport of the plants to the site is accounted for. A planting density of four plants per square meter was assumed, with an average weight of 1 kg per plant. The mulch layer was modeled using the "bark chips production, hardwood" flow. Since no specific inventory flow for engineered soil was available in the ecoinvent database, the general excavation flow was selected to approximate material extraction and processing activities.

For replacement components, periodic mulch renewal is a crucial maintenance activity, specifically in BRCs subject to heavy metal accumulation (NCDEQ, 2018a). In this case, where only moderate accumulation is expected, a single replacement at mid-system lifetime is assumed. As the vegetation densifies over time, reducing the available space, it is expected that only 40% of the initial mulch volume will need to be replaced.

Energy consumption for vegetation maintenance follows the same approach as in CS4a, using a trimmer for routine maintenance. Over 30 years, it is estimated that this maintenance will require 47 kWh of electricity to run the equipment.

For waste management, a biomass formation rate of 1 kg/m²/year was assumed (PENG et al., 2024), considering only transport to the disposal site without further processing. Mulch disposal was modeled using the "treatment of waste wood, untreated, sanitary landfill" flow. Given its potential metal content, reuse or composting may not be feasible, requiring disposal in sanitary landfills with environmental control measures.

3.4.8 Assumptions for case study 6

CS6d: Improved constructed wetland

A full-scale constructed wetland operating within the same catchment area was used as a reference. This system treats a flow of 500 m³ per day with an influent TSS concentration of 33 mg/L. Using this inventory, the system was resized to accommodate higher influent concentrations, reaching up to 150 mg/L of TSS, while maintaining compliance with established technical standards, including the German guideline DWA-A 262 (2017) and UN-HABITAT (2008).

An increase in the treatment area was considered for influent conditions with low quality, following recommendations such as those from TAYLOR (1992), which suggest that as water quality deteriorates, the treatment area should be proportionally increased. The final dimensions were determined based on standard area values per population equivalent (PE) and considering a constant flow of 500 m³/day. First, the volume of the sedimentation tank was increased from 100 m³ to 250 m³, extending the hydraulic retention time (HRT) from 4.8 hours to 12 hours, as indicated by UN-HABITAT (2008).

For the Vertical Flow Constructed Wetland (VFCW), the area was increased from 430 m² to 2000 m², maintaining a depth of 0.6 m and a porosity of 35%. The hydraulic retention time (HRT) increased from 4.33 to 20.16 hours. The specific area applied was 1.20 m² per equivalent inhabitant, with a specific inflow water volume of 150 L/PE, for treating a population equivalent of 1666.67 (UN-HABITAT, 2008).

Similarly, the Horizontal Flow Constructed Wetland (HFCW) expanded from 670 m² to 2666.67 m², with the HRT increasing from 6.75 hours to 26.88 hours, in line with literature recommendations for influents with high load (TAYLOR, 1992). This component used a specific area of 1.60 m² per equivalent inhabitant, designed to serve 1666.67 inhabitants (UN-HABITAT, 2008). A detailed specification of the upscaled configuration is provided in Table A 12 of the appendix.

To provide consistency with the full-scale reference system and the constructed wetland, the next step involved defining the assumptions for the construction and operational phases. The excavation volume was calculated to account for the soil removal to implement the underground sedimentation tank and integrate the hybrid constructed wetland. Reinforced concrete is used in the sedimentation tank, maintaining the same ratio as in previous tanks, with 150 kg of steel per cubic meter. Concrete is also used in the water level control structures located downstream of the vertical and horizontal flow constructed wetlands, which regulate the water level and control the outflow.

The constructed wetland substrate is composed of coarse and fine gravel materials. A 20-40 mm gravel layer is placed at the bottom of the VFCW at a depth of 0.15 m, while the HFCW consists of two gravel layers, each 0.2 m thick. A 5-10 mm gravel layer forms the upper layer of the VFCW, with a thickness of 0.45 m, and is also used as the intermediate layer in the HFCW, with a thickness of 0.2 m. The system is vegetated with *Phragmites Australis*, planted at a density of 10 plants per square meter.

The VFCW includes a central DN100 PVC distribution pipeline that extends throughout the system, with a length of 113.16 meters. This main pipe evenly distributes the incoming water through a network of perpendicular secondary pipes, also of DN100 PVC, spaced every 3 meters, with a total length of 779.83 meters. A similar piping arrangement is applied in the wetland bottom drainage system to facilitate uniform water collection. In the HFCW, the inlet and outlet pipes are DN100 PVC, each 39.71 meters long.

The connections between the settling tank and the VFCW consist of DN250 HDPE pipes, including the inlet pipe to the settling tank, the overflow pipe, and the outlet pipe to the VFCW, with a combined total length of 40 meters. In addition, geotextile layers are incorporated into the wetland substrate, along with a pond liner, which provides protection to minimize seepage.

The operational phase includes regular plant trimming and biomass collection. To accurately account for the energy consumption associated with trimming, the analysis incorporates the electricity required for the operation of the machine. The total area requiring maintenance is 5,834 m², and the time required per session was estimated using a maintenance rate of 200 m² per hour, resulting in an operating time of approximately 7.78 hours per session. Over a year,

this corresponds to 23.33 operating hours, and over 30 years the total reaches 700.05 operating hours. The electric trimmer is assumed to consume 0.6 kW per hour, leading to a total energy consumption of 420.03 kW over the lifetime of the CWs.

In addition to vegetation maintenance, energy is required to pump water from the sedimentation tank to the constructed wetland. This process consumes 4.17 Wh per cubic meter of treated water.

The biomass fraction designated for composting accounts for 30 percent of the total mass, as indicated by the team at ISSBAT. Over the operational period, this corresponds to an estimated 71,400 kg. The calculation is based on an average biomass production rate of 1.3 kg/m²/year, which aligns with the reported range of 1.0 to 1.5 kg/m²/year, according to PENG et al. (2024).

4 Results

The third phase in the LCA methodology involves impact assessment, where the inventory is translated into the different impacts within the selected categories (Figure D 1). The LCIA was conducted using the ReCiPe method for the characterization of mid-point impact indicators.

In order to facilitate analysis and interpretation, the impact categories are grouped into two perspectives. The first reflects a direct impact on water bodies, such as eutrophication and ecotoxicity, where point source emissions become relevant. The second perspective considers those categories where anthropogenic activities, such as industrial production and operation processes, have a wider range of exposure, including effects not only in aquatic environments but also in direct impact on the atmosphere (infrastructure-related impacts).

Absolute results for the construction and operation phase and the PSEs are presented below, the relative results for materials and services in each phase are provided in Appendix D 3. Regarding the classification of materials and services, the same approach is followed as the one presented in the inventories. For instance, when referring to input materials, it is recommended to consult the corresponding inventory to allocate the materials included in this section.

4.1 Combined sewer overflow technologies for mean concentrations

4.1.1 Case study 1

The results for the different scenarios in case study 1 in the various impact categories are summarized in Figure 4.1. In the GWP, TAP, and WCP categories, scenarios CS1e and CS1f record the highest impacts, mainly due to the significant contribution of the operation phase. In terms of GWP, the implementation of the RSF “as built” (CS1d) generates a reduction of 2.5 million kg CO₂-eq compared to the tank storage scenario (CS1c). However, this reduction does not remain when analyzing the compact RSF scenarios (CS1e and CS1f), as the impacts from the operation phase offset the benefits observed in the construction phase.

In terms of construction, both compact scenarios exhibit lower impacts in comparison to CS1c and CS1d. CS1f is the scenario with the lowest impact in the construction phase (4.35×10^6 kg CO₂-eq), while CS1c registers the highest value (5.45×10^6 kg CO₂-eq). The main contributors to these impacts are concrete, reinforcing steel, and transportation, which account for more than 85% of the total contribution in all scenarios.

Figure 4.1: Environmental Impact Assessment for case study 1

For RSF, the relative contribution of materials varies between scenarios. In CS1d, CS1e and CS1f, reinforcing steel is the main contributor, with a share of 30 to 39% of the total impact. In CS1d the second contributor is transportation, while in the compact variants, it ranks third after concrete. CS1c differs from the other scenarios due to the higher proportion of concrete in its total impact. Unlike CS1d, CS1e and CS1f, where the largest impact comes from reinforcing steel, in CS1c, concrete is the material with the highest contribution. This difference can be attributed to the design assumptions in CS1c, where a 150 kg/m³ ratio of concrete was used, in contrast to the 200 kg/m³ ratio used in CS1d according to the RSF “as built” inventory data provided by the ATD team.

Despite the variation in the materials relative contributions, there is no evidence of strong differences between the systems, as there is a compensation between the materials used. For instance, although CS1c requires larger amounts of concrete and reinforcing steel than the other scenarios, its impacts are offset by lower contributions in transportation, plastics and natural materials such as gravel and sand. Thus, what is increased in one component is reduced in another.

The transition from CS1d to the compact variants CS1e and CS1f achieves an overall impact reduction of 12% and 17% in the construction phase. However, this benefit does not extend to the operational phase, where the differences become pronounced. The RSF, in its compact scenarios, has the highest impact, while the as-built system generates practically no impact during operation. This variance is attributed to the intensive use of the chitosan solution during the 30-year lifetime of the compact configurations. As indicated in section 2.2.1, this material, under current development conditions, generates a considerable environmental burden. In these scenarios, using biofloculants accounts for 55% of the total impact, exceeding any savings achieved in the construction phase.

In the METP, the construction phase presents significant impacts in all scenarios. Although, in general, CS1c shows lower overall burdens due to its higher efficiency in heavy metal removal, it is the scenario that reports the highest construction-related impact, reaching 5.19×10^5 kg 1.4-DCB-eq. However, in general, the values of this phase remain within the same order of magnitude in the four scenarios, considering the same explanations presented for the GWP. The main contributor to this impact in this category is reinforced steel, followed by transportation.

Regarding WCP, the impacts are considerably high in scenarios CS1e and CS1f, again due to the use of chitosan. According to the values reported by RIOFRIO et al. (2021), chitosan production consumes approximately 34 m³ of water per kg of material. Overall consumption in these scenarios exceeds 4 million m³ of water.

4.1.2 Case study 3

The results of the scenarios assessed in case study 3 are presented in Figure 4.2. The highest environmental benefits are observed in CS3b, where the capacity of the treatment plant is extended through operational optimization, avoiding additional infrastructures. In contrast, implementing a storage tank in CS3c increases environmental impacts due to the high demand for raw materials. Regardless of these structural differences, the operational variations between CS3b and CS3c remain minimal. Compared to CS3b, CS3c has a slightly higher impact due to the additional energy consumption required to pump the water to the treatment plant, which increases by 5%.

Figure 4.2: Environmental Impact Assessment for case study 3

In the GWP category, the impact of CS3b is 62% lower compared to CS3c. The contribution from operation reaches 2.54×10^6 kg CO₂-eq for CS3b and 2.67×10^6 kg CO₂-eq for CS3c, with 92% of the overall burden attributed to energy consumption. The remaining impacts come from operating inputs (flocculant) and replacement components, albeit in a smaller proportion. The impact associated with the construction of CS3c corresponds to 4.09×10^6 kg CO₂-eq, with concrete (43%) and reinforcing steel (35%) accounting for the most significant contributions.

In the acidification category, CS3b records a total impact of 8.97×10^3 kg SO₂-eq, whereas CS3c reaches 1.91×10^4 kg SO₂-eq. The construction phase alone contributes 9.68×10^3 kg

SO₂-eq, with reinforcing steel (35%) and concrete (36%) accounting for the largest shares. Transportation also plays a significant role, contributing around 20% of the total emissions. During operation, acidification impacts in both scenarios are primarily driven by energy consumption, which accounts for more than 90% of total contributions.

CS3b and CS3c achieve the same pollutant removal efficiency, leading to similar reductions in PSEs. In the eutrophication categories, implementing the scenarios CS3b and CS3c results in a substantial reduction of phosphorus (90%) and nitrogen (80%) emissions compared to CS3a. Emissions from the life cycle of these systems remain minimal in comparison to the impact of effluent discharge. In CS3b, PSE accounts for 94% of total impacts in freshwater eutrophication and 99% in marine, while CS3c exhibits similar values at 92% and 99%, respectively.

Regarding ecotoxicity, both systems effectively reduce environmental impacts. CS3b achieves a 91% reduction in FETP associated with heavy metal retention. In METP, CS3b achieves a 90% reduction, whereas CS3c only reaches 70%. Despite both systems having the same pollutant removal efficiency, the construction phase in CS3c accounts for most impacts (66%). This increase is related to reinforcing steel, which contributes 91% of the impacts in this phase.

Water consumption in CS3c is predominant in the operation phase, influenced by energy consumption, accounting for 90%. The same ratio is reported in CS3b.

4.1.3 Case study 6

Figure 4.3 shows the results of the impact categories in the four CS6 scenarios. CS6b presents the lowest results in all categories. In contrast, CS6d produces the largest environmental footprint. For the GWP category, the operation phase of CS6b and CS6c show similar results, with a total impact of 4.66×10^4 kg CO₂-eq and 4.87×10^4 kg CO₂-eq, respectively. In both cases, energy consumption dominates, contributing 93% of the total impact. In the construction phase of CS6c, 1.53×10^5 kg of CO₂-eq are generated, exceeding its operational emissions by 3.1 times. As in CS3c, the main contributors are concrete (45%) and reinforcing steel (38%), materials with high energy consumption in their production processes.

For CS6d, the impact during the construction phase is 59% higher compared to CS6c. The principal drivers are transportation (41%) and plastics (21%). The large impact of transportation suggests a higher dependence on materials mobilization. In addition, reinforcing steel (14%) and concrete (16%) remain relevant factors, but to a lesser extent than in CS6c. In CS6d, operational emissions are 97% lower than the 4.87×10^4 kg CO₂-eq reported in CS6c. The operational phase in CS6d contributes less than 1% to the overall carbon footprint.

Acidification results follow a similar trend to those observed in GWP, with energy consumption accounting for the major share of operational emissions.

In FEP, scenarios CS6b and CS6c achieve a reduction of 89% with respect to CS6a, thus representing a considerable decrease in phosphorus load. In CS6d, the reduction is 74%, indicating lower efficiency. For MEP, a similar trend is observed, with CS6b and CS6c reaching a reduction of 80%, while in CS6d this decrease is 70%.

Figure 4.3: Environmental Impact Assessment for case study 6

In terms of FETP, scenarios CS6b and CS6c present reductions of 91% and 89%, respectively. However, in CS6d the reduction is 47%, showing a significant difference primarily related to its removal efficiency of only 50%. In METP, CS6b achieves a 90% reduction, CS6c 47% and

CS6d 14%. For CS6c, the construction phase is responsible for most of the impact, with reinforcing steel and plastic materials as the main contributors. In the case of CS6d, more than half of the impact is due to system inefficiency.

Water consumption varies between configurations. CS6d presents the highest total consumption ($2.67 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^3$), with a significant contribution from the construction phase, with gravel production being the largest contributor, responsible for 64% of the total water consumption.

4.1.4 Ranking of treatment scenarios

A comparison of the six treatment scenarios (CS1d, CS1e, CS1f, CS3b, CS3c, and CS6d) shows clear differences in environmental impact, with CS3b as the best-performing scenario and CS6d as the least sustainable. Table 4.1 presents the normalized results per cubic meter of treated water. Each scenario is classified within each impact category using a color scheme, with green representing the least polluting option, yellow indicating intermediate performance, and red highlighting the least favorable alternative.

Table 4.1: Life Cycle Impact Assessment per cubic meter of treated CSO water in the mean concentration scenario

Case study Impact category	CS1d	CS1e	CS1f	CS3b	CS3c	CS6d
Climate change [kg CO ₂ -Eq/m ³]	1.94E-01	4.24E-01	4.14E-01	9.70E-02	2.58E-01	5.11E-01
Acidification [kg SO ₂ -Eq/m ³]	5.77E-04	1.24E-03	1.22E-03	3.42E-04	7.29E-04	1.43E-03
Freshwater eutrophication [kg P-Eq/m ³]	3.05E-04	3.29E-04	3.29E-04	1.59E-04	1.63E-04	3.85E-04
Marine eutrophication [kg N-Eq/m ³]	1.19E-03	1.20E-03	1.20E-03	5.95E-04	5.97E-04	8.97E-04
Freshwater ecotoxicity [kg 1.4-DCB-Eq/m ³]	1.57E-02	1.86E-02	1.86E-02	4.91E-03	5.44E-03	2.78E-02
Marine ecotoxicity [kg 1.4-DCB-Eq/m ³]	3.85E-02	4.41E-02	4.21E-02	7.33E-03	2.18E-02	6.24E-02
Water use [m ³ /m ³]	1.25E-03	1.71E-01	1.71E-01	1.32E-03	2.12E-03	5.58E-03

CS3b ranks first across all impact categories. Compared to CS6d, CS3b has 81% lower GWP emissions, 76% lower acidification impacts, and 82% lower freshwater ecotoxicity levels. In the second position are CS3c and CS1d, whose main difference lies in the balance between material efficiency and pollutant removal capacity.

Regarding resource use, CS1d has 25% lower GWP emissions and 21% lower acidification potential than CS3c. In addition, CS1d consumes 41% less water. However, when considering

pollutant discharge, CS3c performs significantly better, achieving a 47% reduction FEP and a 50% reduction in MEP, compared to the CS1d values. In addition, freshwater ecotoxicity FETP is 65% lower, indicating its higher nutrients and heavy metal retention capacity.

CS1f ranks third, surpassing CS1e, as described in section 4.1.1. Although both scenarios underperform compared to other systems, they achieve better results than CS6d, which ranks last in five of the seven impact categories evaluated.

The normalized results per kg of TSS removed are presented in Table D 2 in the Appendix. The results follow the same tendencies as the normalized values per cubic meter of treated water. No significant variations are observed, as the three technologies have comparable TSS removal efficiencies, resulting in similar environmental impact distributions.

4.2 Combined sewer overflow technologies for peak concentrations

The results for the five scenarios in case study 2 are presented in Figure 4.4. Overall, CS2b and CS2c have significantly lower environmental impacts. GWP values in CS2d are seven times higher than in CS2c and increase 37 times in CS2e. A similar trend is observed in TAP, where emissions increase by 18 and 110, respectively, and in WCP, which shows the most pronounced difference, with consumption increasing 22-fold in CS2d compared to CS2c and 175-fold in CS2e. For the remaining impact categories, variability depends on system efficiency, as previously stated.

The environmental impact of CS2 varies considerably between the two filtration-adsorption scenarios. The main differences occur in the operation phase, where the demand for inputs required for the desorption process increases dramatically when the regenerant solution is not reused. In CS2e, the operating inputs are almost 11 times higher than in CS2d, mainly due to sodium bicarbonate and sodium chloride production. Similar effects are found in all impact categories in the operation phase of both systems.

The construction phase is identical for both systems; thus, the impacts do not vary within the same category. The construction GWP (6.93×10^5 kg CO₂-eq) is driven mainly by natural and composite materials, contributing 57% of the total impact. Within this fraction, 43% is attributed to sodium carbonate production and 39% to zeolite. Stainless steel (19%) also contributes to the GWP impact, mainly due to its use in constructing adsorption and desorption columns. Additionally, transportation represents 17% of the construction phase impact. Particularly, maritime transport of zeolite from China to Europe accounts for 8% of the total GWP.

Figure 4.4: Environmental Impact Assessment for case study 2

In FEP, CS2d is influenced mainly by PSEs (75%), followed by operation (15%) and construction (10%). However, CS2e shows a considerable increase in emissions, with 61% of its total impact attributed to the operation phase, specifically sodium carbonate production. Similarly, in MEP, the operation phase emerges as the dominant contributor. For METP, the operational contribution of CS2d represents 11% of the total impact, and for CS2e, this percentage rises to 57%. Further indicating the substantial effect of sodium carbonate production on the overall environmental burden of the system.

The ranking of the technologies is further documented in the normalized results per cubic meter of water treated (Table 4.2) and per kilogram of TSS removed (Table D 3). As shown in the

overall figures, CS2b is the most viable option, followed by CS2c. CS2d is third, while CS2e has the highest environmental loads, ranking last in all impact categories.

Table 4.2: Life Cycle Impact Assessment per cubic meter of treated CSO water in the peak concentration scenario

Case study Impact category	CS2b	CS2c	CS2d	CS2e
Climate change [kg CO ₂ -Eq/m ³]	1.13E-01	4.13E-01	2.91E+00	1.56E+01
Acidification [kg SO ₂ -Eq/m ³]	4.14E-04	1.19E-03	2.16E-02	1.30E-01
Freshwater eutrophication [kg P-Eq/m ³]	5.10E-04	5.18E-04	7.30E-04	1.81E-03
Marine eutrophication [kg N-Eq/m ³]	2.38E-03	2.38E-03	4.87E-03	5.62E-03
Freshwater ecotoxicity [kg 1.4-DCB-Eq/m ³]	9.05E-02	9.15E-02	9.65E-02	1.17E-01
Marine ecotoxicity [kg 1.4-DCB-Eq/m ³]	1.27E-01	1.55E-01	1.90E-01	3.89E-01
Water use [m ³ /m ³]	1.46E-03	3.01E-03	6.78E-02	5.29E-01

4.3 Urban runoff treatment systems

The results for the urban runoff scenarios are presented in Figure 4.5. Scenario CS0c presents the highest environmental impacts in terms of GWP and TAP compared to all other scenarios. Within the SuDS technologies, the CS4b system has the second highest GWP impact, reaching 3.33 x 10⁴ kg CO₂-eq.

Scenario CS4a [redacted], whereas CS5 achieves a 66% reduction. For CS4a, the main source is transportation, with a contribution of 39% in the construction phase and 50% in the operational phase. It is followed by natural materials (24%), and plastics (22%), both within the construction phase. For CS5, the greatest impact is also found in the construction phase, with 83% of its emissions attributable to transportation.

Regarding TAP, the scenarios follow the same order as in GWP, with the main responsible for emissions corresponding to the same materials previously identified. For FEP, CS0b and CS0c systems show the highest efficiency in phosphorus removal, with the main contributions derived from the PSE. Within the three SUDS, CS4b presents the highest efficiency, reaching 55% removal, in contrast to CS4a and CS5 systems, with only 30% removal. For MEP, although CS4b performs better in terms of treatment efficiency, [redacted]

The impacts for CS4a and CS5 relate to the PSE; the removal efficiency corresponds to 49% and 30%, respectively.

Figure 4.5: Environmental Impact Assessment for urban runoff systems

In FETP, CS5 has the lowest footprint, bettering that CS0c, which has an increased impact due to the construction phase. [redacted] while CS4a increases it by 2.8 times. [redacted] CS4a and CS5 perform better in METP than CS0c. For WCP, these scenarios not only show lower impacts than CS0c, but also than CS0b. Evidence for this is the lower toxicity of the materials used in their construction and lower dependence on water consumption.

The evaluation of the five urban runoff management scenarios shows variations in environmental performance. The WWTP operation (CS0b) is the best sustainable option. CS0b registers the lowest impact in multiple categories, including GWP, TAP, FEP, MEP, FETP, and METP, as reflected in the normalized rankings in Table 4.3 and Table D 4 in the appendix.

The bioretention cell (CS5) appears in the second position, with a low environmental load in most categories. However, its nutrient removal efficiency is low, leading to higher eutrophication impacts than other scenarios.

Table 4.3: Life Cycle Impact Assessment per cubic meter of treated water in the urban runoff management

Case study	CS0b	CS0c	CS4a		CS5
Climate change [kg CO ₂ -Eq/m ³]	9.35E-02	1.08E+00	1.97E-01		1.20E-01
Acidification [kg SO ₂ -Eq/m ³]	3.25E-04	2.83E-03	5.69E-04		3.58E-04
Freshwater eutrophication [kg P-Eq/m ³]	3.87E-05	6.55E-05	2.13E-04		2.11E-04
Marine eutrophication [kg N-Eq/m ³]	1.79E-04	1.92E-04	4.57E-04		6.25E-04
Freshwater ecotoxicity [kg 1.4-DCB-Eq/m ³]	4.84E-03	8.25E-03	2.30E-02		7.07E-03
Marine ecotoxicity [kg 1.4-DCB-Eq/m ³]	7.13E-03	1.04E-01	3.57E-02		1.24E-02
Water use [m ³ /m ³]	1.30E-03	6.32E-03	1.17E-03		8.94E-04

The sand filter (CS4a) and the storage tank (CS0c) have intermediate performance, with trade-offs depending on the impact categories. CS0c has higher infrastructure-related impacts (GWP, TAP, and WCP) than CS4a. However, when considering pollutant discharge, CS0c outperforms CS4a in eutrophication and ecotoxicity.

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

5 Discussion

The results of the study suggest that the technologies evaluated significantly improve water quality concerning the no-intervention scenario, especially in terms of eutrophication and ecotoxicity. However, trade-offs emerge for categories relevant to the construction and operation of the systems, namely climate change, acidification, and water use. Thus, a balance in designing and implementing these technologies should be achieved to ensure efficiency in reducing pollutants while avoiding overconsumption of resources.

5.1 Point source-related impacts

Based on the results achieved, it was possible to identify key patterns in the distribution of the environmental impacts of the technologies. In particular, it was observed that in most of the systems, 95% of the impacts in FEP, MEP, and FETP come from point source emissions, while the impacts associated with operation and construction are significantly lower. In the case of marine ecotoxicity (METP), the impacts of the construction phase are more relevant in those systems with a high content of reinforcing steel, as shown in Chapter 2.2, being the material with the highest contribution in this category. [REDACTED]

These impact categories, related to the environmental load on aquatic ecosystems, confirm the benefits of applying the treatment technologies. The results also indicate that this environmental benefit is mainly linked to the capacity of the systems to remove nutrients and heavy metals. Thus, the technology with the highest efficiency in these categories is the smart management of the WWTP or scenario c, with 80% for total nitrogen and 90% for phosphorus. For heavy metals, the removal ranges from 65% to 95%.

Implementing a storage tank presents the same efficiency, adding a minimal construction impact to eutrophication and ecotoxicity. Regarding CSO treatment, this is the second-best option to manage point source emissions, followed by the retention soil filter. In the case of SuDS, this is the second-best option for eutrophication management, but for ecotoxicity, systems such as BRC and sand filter present a lower environmental load.

5.2 Infrastructure-related impacts

The implementation of treatment technologies improves effluent quality and reduces direct environmental load. However, it can also increase energy demand, material consumption, and emissions associated with their operation (BRUDLER, 2019), leading to infrastructure-related impacts posing increased effects in global warming, acidification, and water consumption.

In these categories, the technology that shows the lowest load is, again, the smart management of the WWTP. For CSO treatment, the second option, if there is no possibility of treatment expansion by WWTP, is the implementation of the RSF, followed by the implementation of the storage tank and at last the improved constructed wetland. It is worth mentioning that this last system has been sized to fit the inlet water quality designed for this group of technologies, however it has been found that under these conditions the system becomes unsustainable, due to the high consumption of materials in the construction phase for a relatively low proportion of its use during its lifespan. The sensitivity to inlet water quality parameters in the system is presented in the section 5.4.1. Exhibiting improved behavior under different conditions.

In terms of SuDS, the systems with the least impact, followed by the WWTP operation, [REDACTED] [REDACTED] The storage tank option is the largest polluter as it involves the use of materials with a high footprint for its construction, for instance, reinforced concrete. In comparison, SuDS use more sustainable alternatives, using aggregates, which, as shown in Table 2.2, are materials with a high environmental profile. Furthermore, it is noted that for these technologies the greatest impact is not generated entirely from the manufacture of these materials, but rather from their transportation. Aligning with the statements reported by LANGER (2016).

In all case studies, scenarios b and c have been evaluated, and comparing these scenarios with each other leads to finding patterns or differences. Scenario b, which represents the operation of the WWTP, does not show significant variations in the functional unit between the different case studies. The only significant difference is observed in case 2, where water treatment with maximum pollutant concentrations causes a greater impact due to the higher demand for flocculants required to reduce phosphorus concentration. The FU remains relatively constant in all case studies for the rest of the technologies.

In the analysis of storage tanks (scenario c), considerable variations are observed among the different case studies. The smaller the tank, the lower the environmental efficiency since the high material requirements for its construction are not fully justified by the reduced volume of water treated during its useful life. However, this trend is not present in all cases. The CS1b and CS3b systems treat the same flow in a year. However, CS1b is larger than CS3b,

presenting a less favorable environmental performance in terms of impact per cubic meter treated due to more material required for its construction.

The difference lies primarily in the technological and operational context of each case study. The system in Birs, despite having a smaller connection of “person equivalent” and a storage capacity of 32,000 m³ compared to 45,000 m³ in Aachen, manages to process about 900,000 m³ of water per year, a figure similar to that of the RSF system. This is partly explained by less peak flows, which allow for more constant emptying and filling throughout the year.

5.3 Scope limitations

The impact of a technology depends not only on its design or removal efficiency but also on the specific conditions of the site where it is implemented. Therefore, the results should be carefully interpreted, as the analysis has been performed on a case-specific basis, considering a fixed input concentration and assuming constant efficiency over time without including possible yield losses. By using this approach, the conditions for all technologies were standardized and the comparison was facilitated. However, the results show that the performance of the systems depends on the characteristics of the water treated. For instance, due to their limited removal capacity, the sand filter and bioretention systems operate more efficiently in waters with low nutrient concentrations. Similarly, the constructed wetland shows better environmental performance when the water has low concentrations of heavy metals.

It is not enough to assess the environmental sustainability of a technology. It is essential to consider its technical performance, ensuring that it is adapted to the specific site conditions and treatment objectives. In all cases, the objective should be to contribute to the achievement of the chemical and biological good status of water bodies, in accordance with the Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) defined in Directive 2008/105/EC for surface water and the Directive 2006/118/EC for the prevention of groundwater pollution (EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, 2006, 2008).

The most appropriate technology should be selected according to the level of water quality to be achieved and the environmental benefits associated. In this regard, the results of this study cannot be generalized to other contexts, as the environmental assessment may vary significantly depending on the system boundaries, methodological assumptions, and particularly the geographic region considered (SPATARI et al., 2011). This, in turn, limits the possibility of a direct comparison between the impacts calculated in this study and those reported in the literature.

For this study, Europe is the reference area for comparison, which implies that the reported environmental impacts represent an average of the materials and services within the established geographical boundaries. However, there may be relevant discrepancies between

countries even within the same continent. This implies that the implementation of a specific technology in Italy may represent a different environmental burden in Germany due to factors such as the degree of industrial decarbonization, which is directly linked to the composition of the energy mix of the country in question (GAJDZIK et al., 2024). As presented in 2.2.2, the transition from a coal-based energy source to wind power allows reducing the impacts associated with Global Warming Potential (GWP) by up to 97%, highlighting the importance of decarbonization in mitigating environmental impacts.

5.4 Sensitivity analysis

The inventories of the construction and operation phases of the systems are influenced by the uncertainty of the parameters used, including aspects such as the amount of materials required for construction, transport distances, or the environmental impact associated with the choice between two alternative solutions that perform the same function but differ in terms of sustainability. Many of these uncertainties originate because the systems evaluated are still in the development phase, making it difficult to accurately measure specific parameters until the establishment is completed.

To assess the sensitivity of the results, alternative parameter values are tested that either contribute significantly to the total impacts or are characterized by a high degree of uncertainty (HUIJBREGTS, 1998). According to BRUDLER (2019), when parameters are within physically defined limits, it is sufficient to analyze the most optimistic or most pessimistic scenarios to understand the possible variations in the results. Therefore, for each case study, an optimistic sensitivity scenario (s) is presented, in which specific parameters are adjusted to evaluate the behavior of the system under objective conditions and identify the main contributors to the environmental impacts.

5.4.1 Combined sewer overflow technologies for mean concentrations

Case study 1

Chitosan represents the primary source of uncertainty in the analysis due to the lack of studies assessing its production on an industrial scale. The values used in this research are derived from literature and constitute a first approximation. However, methodological limitations are present since these assessments are limited to small-scale processes, and their extrapolation to industrial applications again introduces uncertainty. However, under industrial conditions, the environmental impact of chitosan is expected to be moderate, as large-scale production generally lead to improved resource efficiency (PICCINNO et al., 2016).

The highest impacts related to chitosan application are observed in GWP and WCP in Figure 5.1. To assess how the contributions would change under different impact factors, a best-case

scenario (s) was developed, assuming that industrial-scale production would reduce environmental impacts by 95%. Under these conditions, the impact factor for GWP would decrease per kilogram of chitosan from 43.5 kg CO₂ eq to 2.2 kg CO₂ eq. Similarly, water consumption would be reduced from 34 m³/kg to 1.7 m³, thus decreasing the total impact in this category from over 4 x 10⁶ m³ to approximately 2.34 x 10⁵ m³.

Figure 5.1: Sensitivity analysis results for GWP and TAP in case study 1

In the best-case scenario, the implementation of the compact RSF would present environmental benefits compared to the storage tank scenario, corresponding to a reduction of approximately 2 x 10⁶ kg CO₂ eq. However, compared to the “as-built” scenario, the compact configurations still show higher overall impacts. Additional sensitivity analysis results can be found in Figure D 33, in the Appendix.

The systems compared in this first case study are characterized by a high use of concrete and reinforcing steel. For the construction phase, it is recommended that concrete with a low clinker content is chosen, while maintaining the required strength. For future research, it is suggested to study the environmental performance of the selection of a more sustainable concrete.

Case study 3

The results highlight the significant role of electricity consumption in the overall environmental impacts. To assess the influence of the energy source, the electricity mix was modified, shifting to a 100% renewable supply powered by wind energy. The inventory flows to produce 1 kWh using renewable energy are provided in Table C 33 in the appendix.

A key difference observed is the reduction in the GWP impact factor. It decreases from 0.33 kg CO₂ eq per kWh to 0.032 kg CO₂ eq per kWh, representing a 90% reduction in energy-related emissions. At the system level, this change translates into an 84% reduction in CO₂ emissions for CS3b and 33% for CS3c, as illustrated in Figure D 34.

A similar trend is observed in acidification, where CS3b achieves an 82% reduction in SO₂-eq emissions, while CS3c records a 40% decrease. In FEP, MEP, and FETP, operational

emissions decreased by 92%, 50%, and 55%, respectively. However, the overall impact remains essentially unchanged, as these categories are primarily influenced by PSEs.

METP and WCP do not show the same improvements as the previous categories. METP exhibits a slight increase in 1.4-DCB-Eq during operation by 50%. However, regarding total impact, this represents only a 4% increase in CS3b and 1.5% in CS3c. WCP emerges as the category with the most significant adverse effects, with additional water consumption of $72 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^3$ in CS3b and $75.8 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^3$ in CS3c, representing increases of 209% and 139%, respectively. It should be noted that this increase in water consumption is not linked to power generation but to the transformation of electricity from high voltage to medium voltage, accounting for 98% of total water consumption. Electricity generation requires 0.00017 m^3 per kWh, whereas the transformation process contributes 0.014 m^3 per kWh.

A shift in energy source denotes significant environmental savings, considerable for climate change and acidification, in the future this is projected to be a viable option. However, it is observed that a tradeoff is created, marine ecotoxicity and water consumption increase. For further research it is recommended to explore other renewable energy sources and to identify, as in the case of wind energy, the possible advantages and drawbacks.

Case study 6

In the LCI phase, a high dependence of the constructed wetland on the quality of the water to be treated was observed. The higher the level of contamination, the larger the treatment area required, leading to a higher consumption of raw materials during construction. Improved inlet water, in turn, reduces the overall environmental impact. An alternative scenario was considered to address the sensitivity of this dependency, considering a higher inlet water quality, with a TSS concentration of 33 mg/L instead of 170 mg/L.

The results for the impact categories in the sensitivity scenario for CS6d (s) are presented in Figure D 35. System data can be found in Appendix A, Table A 13. Impacts of CS6b and CS6c are assumed to remain unaffected. For CS6c, the storage tank maintains the same size, as volume is the conditioning parameter. In the case of WWTP, a lower TSS load is generally associated with reduced sludge production. However, since sludge management is beyond the system boundaries of this study, this effect is not further analyzed.

Significant impact reductions are observed. GWP emissions decrease by 66%. A similar trend is observed in TAP, with a 67% reduction in SO_2 -equivalent emissions. For FEP, MEP and FETP, the overall reduction is marginal. These categories are mainly influenced by the performance of the system, which remains unchanged. However, METP shows a notable decrease (24%), owing to the reduction in reinforced steel use in the sedimentation tank. In addition, water consumption decreases by 71%.

The constructed wetland has a significantly lower carbon footprint compared to the storage tank in this new design, achieving approximately 50% savings. However, when compared to CS6b, it still shows a higher overall impact. A similar trend is observed for TAP and WCP. For the remaining impact categories, variations are minimal.

As shown in section 4.1.4, the ranking placed the improved constructed wetland in the last position, mainly due to its lower efficiency in treating priority parameters for point source emissions, such as heavy metals. However, as the sensitivity analysis shows, this technology can provide significant benefits, subject to the right conditions.

5.4.2 Combined sewer overflow technologies for peak concentrations

The results emphasize the critical role of regenerant solution reuse in reducing the environmental burden of the filtration-adsorption system. The elimination of regenerant recycling in CS2e results in an order-of-magnitude increase in climate change impacts, reinforcing the necessity of optimizing regenerant management to ensure the sustainability of the system.

Based on the results, sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) production stands out as the primary source of the environmental impact of the system. Its manufacture requires significant heat inputs (ecoinvent v3.10), thus strongly influencing its environmental footprint. In addition to sodium carbonate, zeolite (MS13X) production represents also a substantial contributor. However, there is considerable uncertainty in the impact factors used for this material, as the data obtained are derived from generic zeolite transformation processes and not from specific MS13X data sets. Additionally, the inventory is based on a 1998 study. Although more recent data on production flows have been integrated, there may be considerable variations in current industrial processes, affecting the accuracy of the results.

A best-case scenario, as presented in CS1, allows for verifying the influence of materials. However, since a modification of the impact factors has already been found to be decisive in the environmental assessment of the system, a complementary approach is proposed in this sensitivity analysis. Currently, the global supply of MS13X depends mainly on the Chinese market. This implies impacts associated with the maritime transport of large volumes of zeolite for CS2d, reaching up to 47 tons per plant. In this context, the present sensitivity analysis aims to identify the potential benefits of a European-based zeolite supply, thus eliminating emissions from long-distance maritime transport. The CS2d scenario is not considered in the sensitivity analysis, as previous results indicate that the recycling of the regenerant solution represents the alternative with the lowest environmental impact and the highest operational efficiency.

The sensitivity results, presented in Figure D 36, reflect a moderate reduction in environmental impacts in several categories. The most notable decreases are observed in GWP and TAP,

while the effects on other categories are limited. In terms of GWP, total impacts are reduced from 1.31×10^6 kg CO₂-eq in CS2d to 1.20×10^6 kg CO₂-eq in CS2d (s), representing a decrease of 8.17%. In the case of TAP, a reduction of 20.23% is observed, from 9.70×10^3 kg SO₂-eq to 7.73×10^3 kg SO₂-eq. The analysis indicates that maritime transport is a major source of carbon dioxide and sulfur oxide emissions, probably due to the combustion of fossil fuels.

Despite decreased transport-related impacts, scenarios CS2b and CS2c still exhibit lower environmental burdens than CS2d. Moreover, these results further highlight the relevance of optimizing the production of consumables, including MS13X and Sorbacid and improving it at the industrial level in Europe. Until the industrial production of MS13X and Sorbacid is consolidated on a large scale, the environmental impact of the filtration-adsorption plant will continue to depend on the evolution of these materials in terms of availability and production efficiency.

5.4.3 Urban runoff treatment systems

According to the results, within the systems evaluated, transportation is one of the flows with the most significant influence on environmental impact, in specific cases even exceeding the combined impact of all materials used. This is due to the nature of the materials, mainly aggregates, which, as reviewed in section 2.2.1 present the lowest impact compared to other inputs.

To evaluate the sensitivity of the systems to transport distances, a best-case scenario was designed in which the distance of excavated material was reduced from 50 km to 20 km. Figure D 37 provides the assessment findings.

The most notable environmental benefits are observed in GWP and TAP. Transportation is particularly relevant in these categories due to the emissions associated with fossil fuel combustion. For GWP, the reduction in transport distance generates a decrease of 2.4% in CS0c. In contrast, the improvement is considerably higher for urban drainage systems, with a decrease of 14.3% in CS4a, [REDACTED], and 26.9% in CS5. As for the reduction in TAP, it is of similar proportions. For CS0c of 2.7%, CS4a 14.55%; [REDACTED] and CS5 26.3%. No benefit was observed for the categories relevant to PSE. The reductions are smaller for water consumption, with 3.7% for CS4a, [REDACTED], and 5.6% for CS5.

The sensitivity analysis suggests that targeting suppliers closest to the installation site is critical to reducing the impact. In addition, the feasibility of alternative transportation options, such as vehicles driven by renewable energy sources, as discussed in 2.2.2, could be explored to further reduce the contribution of transport to the overall impact of the systems.

6 Conclusions

This study presents the environmental evaluation of different stormwater management technologies applying the Life Cycle Assessment approach. The technologies investigated were classified into combined sewer overflow and runoff management. For each case study, system boundaries were established, and process inventories were prepared for the construction and operation phases. Technologies performing the same function were ranked, and their environmental impact was compared with baseline scenarios, consisting of no intervention, implementation of a storage tank, and treatment at the WWTP. The analysis was performed using the ecoinvent v3.10 database and OpenLCA software.

6.1 Key findings from environmental impact analyses

The results indicate that non-intervention causes the most significant impacts in the categories of eutrophication and ecotoxicity; mitigation is achieved through stormwater treatment technologies, providing an effective solution for protecting the receiving waters. The determining factor for impact reduction is the removal efficiency of phosphorus, nitrogen, and heavy metals. Reducing the load in eutrophication and ecotoxicity, however, generates a trade-off in infrastructure-relevant categories regarding climate change, acidification, and water use. Consequently, this analysis underscores the need for a balanced approach when selecting management technologies.

For both types of management technologies, the WWTP smart management showed the most beneficial results in all impact categories. However, it is only applicable in the absence of physical expansion. Furthermore, the following results were obtained in terms of CSO treatment:

- The RSF “as-built” represents a more sustainable alternative to a storage tank, reducing emissions by 2.5 million kg CO₂-eq over a 30-year implementation period. Using a compact variant of the RSF can further reduce the environmental footprint by up to 17% during construction. However, these benefits are offset by the high consumption of bioflocculant during operation, reducing its viability.
- The impacts on GWP in the filtration-adsorption system with recycling of the desorption solution are seven times higher than those of the storage tank. When no recycling is applied, the impact increases significantly, reaching 37 times the emissions of the storage tank.
- Technologies with a high influence of novel consumables tend to have the highest impacts, due to their dependence on production processes still in the development stage. This concerns the compact RSF, with the use of chitosan, and the adsorption-filtration system with the MS13X zeolite and the Sorbacid 911 hydrotalcite.

- The improved CW performs better environmentally as water quality increases, specifically due to their dependence on the TSS concentration for design. Compared to the other technologies, CW showed the lowest environmental performance, primarily due to its low efficiency in heavy metal removal, which reached only 50%.

Regarding runoff management, the evaluated systems, bioretention cell, sand filter, and shell filter have a lower infrastructure-related environmental impact than the concrete storage tank, reducing the CO₂ footprint by 95%, 80%, and 63%, respectively. The bioretention cell achieves the second-best performance; however, it has a limited nutrient removal efficiency (30%), resulting in a higher burden on eutrophication. Transport represents a significant impact driver, accounting for 83% of the impact in the construction phase for the bioretention cell, 40% for the sand filter, and 36% for the shell filter.

6.2 Directions for future research

The inventories developed are based on the estimated systems upscaling with currently available information, as some technologies are still under development and have different levels of technological readiness. As new data becomes available, the inventories can be updated to improve the reliability of the environmental impact assessment.

Some of the technologies evaluated rely primarily on materials with a high environmental burden in categories such as climate change, acidification, and ecotoxicity, particularly metals and concrete. In future research, alternatives, like concrete with lower clinker content, are suggested to be explored. In addition, addressing transportation has the potential for pollution reduction. Apart from decreasing distances, further studies should be carried out on implementing alternatives such as electric or biofuel vehicles.

Further clarification is required on the impact of the shell filter on marine ecotoxicity and water use. Ongoing communication with the research team is expected to provide insights into the sources of these effects. After identifying the contributors, it will be necessary to review its suitability for comparison with the other SuDS.

When applying sustainability principles, beyond considering the technological and environmental aspects, it is also essential to consider the economic and social aspects. Cost analysis through Life-Cycle Cost Analysis (LCCA) and social implications through Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) could be added to this work.

Finally, the development of inventories was the main limitation of this study. The time required for bilateral communication and literature review reduced the time available for modeling and iteration. As a result, a review of system boundaries is needed, particularly for the improved constructed wetland, which showed greater efficiency under different input parameters.

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Appendix

A Systems descriptions

B Goal and Scope

C Life Cycle Inventory data

D Life Cycle Impact Assessment

Appendix A: Systems descriptions

A 1. Catchment characteristics

A 2. Water quality

A 3. Input data for scaling

Appendix A 1. Catchment characteristics

Table A 1: Site characteristics and configurations of urban catchment systems

Site	CS1 Aachen	CS2 Bologna	CS3 Birsfelden	CS5 Trondheim	CS6 Tunis	CS4A Wolvenberg	CS4B Wetteren
Size	2,650 ha	5,500 ha	4,500 ha	15	22,000 ha (of which 2,900 wetland)	3.8 ha	0.55 ha
Annual rainfall (mm/a)	832	800	840	810	470	852	834
Impervious area (%)	53	47 of built- up/sewered area	57 of built- up/sewered area	50.5	40	75	100
Sewer system	Combined (industrial areas separate rainwater)	Combined (new developments with separate system)	Combined (some municipalities have separate sewers)	Combined (part of catchment was separated in 2022)	Combined / separate	Separate	Separate
Receiving water(s)	Wurm, Rur, Maas	Navile channel – Reno – Adriatic Sea?	Birs, Rhein	Harbour	Sebkha Sijoumi wetland	Pond, groundwater	Molenbeek - Schelde
Protection good and uses of receiving water	Habitat, potentially irrigation	Habitat	Habitat, leisure/bathing	Informal but de facto bathing site	Habitat, Ramsar site	Playground, park	Playground, irrigation of community garden
Surface water status (chemical/ecological)	Not good / not satisfactory	Not good	Good to medium	Bad	Not applicable	Bad	Not applicable
Governing water legislation	WFD, OGewV	WFD	WPA, WPO	National legislation	National legislation	n.a.	n.a.

Source: Deliverable D1.1, "Pollution and Pollution Induced Risk Profiling of Urban Catchments" by Rita Hochstrat, FHNW

Appendix A 2. Water quality

Table A 2: Concentrations of pollutants in CSO reported in the literature

Parameter	Reference									
	Métadier, 2012	Métadier, 2012	Sandoval, 2013	Gamerith, 2011	Baum, 2021	Brombach, 2005	Nickel, 2021	Seibert, 2004	Seibert, 2004	This study
Location	Ecully (Lyon, France)	Chassieu (Lyon, France)	Berlin, Germany	Graz, Austria	Freiburg im Breisgau, Germany	Germany	Bayern, Germany	Central Europa	World	
Catchment Type	Combined Sewer	Separate sewer	Combined Sewer	Combined Sewer	Stormwater (industrial park)	Combined Sewer	Combined Sewer	Combined Sewer	Combined Sewer	Combined Sewer
TSS (mg/L)										
Min	13	22	22	60	8.95		35	114.2	177.5	
Mean	260	144	248	730	63.4		64	175	264	
Max	1433	1421	580	153	237		96	278	423.3	150
Median							50	228.7	315.9	
COD (mg/L)										
Min	16	54	35	150		141	37	87.2	148	
Mean	441	129	377	310			62	112	274	200
Max	1354	966	908	1400			86	242	435	
Median							62	172.4	305.9	
Ptot (mg/L)										
Mean						1.25	0.92	1.53	3.01	1.5
Nitot (mg/L)										
Mean						12.6	7			10
Cr (µg/L)										
Min					1.6		2.6			
Mean	1.5	7.8			13.4		4.1			6.5
Max					41.9		6			
Median					8.82	21	5.1			
Cu (µg/L)										
Min					14.3		28			
Mean	34.1	32			36.3		37			60
Max					108		50			
Median					26.3	97.5	38			
Zn (µg/L)										
Min					157		91			200
Mean	108	314			350		130			
Max					835		170			
Median					276	280	140			
Cd (µg/L)										
Min					0.1		0.049			
Mean	0.09	0.49			0.21		0.063			0.7
Max					0.1	1.4	0.1			
Median							0.07			
Pb (µg/L)										
Min					0.1		2.1			
Mean	5.3	12.3			0.15		3.4			13
Max					1.28		5.3			
Median					0.1	70	4			
Ni (µg/L)										
Min							2.5			6
Mean	2.4	9.6				12	3			
Max										
Median										

Notes: References: (MÉTADIER and BERTRAND-KRAJEWSKI, 2012; SANDOVAL et al., 2013; BAUM et al., 2021; BROMBACH et al., 2005; NICKEL et al., 2021; SEIBERT and RASEL, 2004; GAMERITH, 2011)

Table A 3: Water quality parameters for comparative assessment of CSO treatment technologies under mean and peak concentration conditions

Parameter	CSO mean	CSO peak	Unit
Total Suspended Solids (TSS)	150	418	mg/L
Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)	200	560	mg/L
Total Nitrogen (TN)	10	40	mg/L
Total Phosphorus (TP)	1.5	5	mg/L
Copper (Cu)	60	973	µg/L
Zinc (Zn)	200	3730	µg/l
Lead (Pb)	13	43	µg/L
Cadmium (Cd)	0.7	2.5	µg/L
Chromium (Cr)	6.5	24.5	µg/L
Nickel (Ni)	6	231	µg/L

Table A 4: Characterization of water quality in drainage systems

Parameter	Unit	CS4a	CS4b	CS5	GÖBEL et al. (2007)
TSS	mg/l	223	72.35	320	12 – 163
COD	mg/l	156	63.65	-	19 – 105
TN	mg/l	2.86	3.27	-	-
TP	mg/l	0.10	0.42	-	0,09 – 0.29
Cr	µg/l	20	-	58	3 – 13
Cu	µg/l	70	-	54	11 – 2600
Zn	µg/l	180	51.75	300	80 -6000
Cd	µg/l	10	4.15	0.10	0.7 -3.7
Pb	µg/l	40	11	11	9 -224

Ni	µg/l	10	10	37	2 -27
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Table A 5: Water quality parameters for comparative assessment of runoff treatment technologies

Parameter	Value	Unit
Total Suspended Solids (TSS)	200	mg/L
Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)	100	mg/L
Total Nitrogen (TN)	3	mg/L
Total Phosphorus (TP)	0.3	mg/L
Copper (Cu)	60	µg/L
Zinc (Zn)	180	µg/L
Lead (Pb)	20	µg/L
Cadmium (Cd)	5	µg/L
Chromium (Cr)	40	µg/L
Nickel (Ni)	19	µg/L

Appendix A3. Input data for scaling

Figure A 1: Schematic representation of the filtration-adsorption system for CSO treatment

Table A 6: Hydrological parameters and system characteristics for urban runoff management

Parameter	Value	Unit
Annual precipitation	800	mm
Return period	5	years
Precipitation of return period	40	mm
Runoff coefficient	0.9	
Catchment area	4,400	m ²
Water treated in 1 year	3,168	m ³
Lifespan	30	years
Water treated over lifespan	95,040	m ³
Normative buffer capacity	158.4	m ³

Table A 7: Storage tank specifications by case study

Parameter	CS1	CS2	CS3	CS4, CS5	CS6
Volume (m ³)	45,000	468	32,400	158.40	500
Length (m)	60	14.42	60	14.08	14.91

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Height (m)	6.82	4.50	6.82	2.50	4.50
Area (m ²)	6,600	104	4,752	63.36	111.11
Width (m)	110	7.21	79.20	4.50	7.45
Number of Basins	10	1	7	1	1
Specific energy consumption (kWh/m ³)	0.014	0.009	0.014	0.005	0.009

Table A 8: Comparison of system characteristics and dimensions for CS4a

System Component	Original Design	New Design
Buffer tank (m ³)	560	142.45
Retention volume filter (m ³)	62.7	15.95
Ratio buffer - filter	9:1	9:1
Total capacity (m ³)	622.7	158.4
Filter volume (m ³)	190	48.33
Height	0.7	0.7
Area (m ²)	271.4	69.04
Length (m)	18	9.1
Width (m)	15	7.59
Small swale volume (m ³)	632	160.77
Small swale area (m ²)	830	211.13
Small swale height (m)	0.76	0.76
Large swale volume (m ³)	1,500	-
Large swale area (m ²)	1,000	-
Area buffer tank (m ²)	1,470	374.5

Table A 9: System characteristics and dimensions for CS4b

Component	Value	Unit
Filter Volume	273.71	m ³
Filter high	1.20	m
Soil on top	0.30	m
Area	228.09	m ²
length	50.69	m
width	4.50	m

Table A 10: Structural specifications of the sedimentation tank in CS4b system

Component	Value	Unit
Length	2.3	m
Width	4.8	m
Height	1.3	m
Area	11.04	m ²
Thickness (Base)	0.2	m
Thickness (Walls, Top)	0.15	m
Manhole Diameter	0.6	m
Storage Volume	9	m ³

Notes:

Estimations based on hydraulic calculations and design specifications provided by WENTINK, R. (06.12.2024).

Table A 11: Volumetric contributions and storage capacity of the BRC

Layer	Parameter	Value	unit
Capacity		158.40	m ³
Surface Ponding	Depth	0.15	m
	Contribution	0.15	m
Mulch Layer	Depth	0.075	m
	Porosity	0.7	-
	Contribution	0.053	m
Filter Media	Depth	0.6	m
	Porosity	0.45	-
	Contribution	0.27	m
Gravel layer	Depth	0.4	m
	Porosity	0.32	-
	Contribution	0.13	m
Storage Capacity	Total Contributions	0.60	m ³ /m ²
BRC high		1.26	m
System Area	Required Area (A)	263	m ²

Notes:

Porosity of Mulch layer (shredded wood) derived from (LID SWM PLANNING AND DESIGN GUIDE CONTRIBUTORS, 2024).

Porosity of Filter layer (sandy loam) derived from (MAH et al., 2018, S. 272).

Porosity of gravel layer derived from (GEOTECHDATA.INFO, 2013).

Table A 12: System characteristics and dimensions for CS6

Parameter	Value	Unit
Flow rate	500	m ³ /d
Settling tank volume	250	m ³
HRT (settling tank)	12	h
Sedimentation velocity	< 0.0015	m/s
Tank dimensions		
Width	5.77	m
Length	17.32	m
Height	2.50	m
Area	100	m ²
Constructed wetland dimensions		
Annual average specific inflow water volume	150	l/E*d
Total daily water treatment	500,000	l/d
Population served by VFCW	1,666.67	E
Population served by HFCW	1,666.67	E
Specific area VFCW	1.20	m ² /E
Specific area HFCW	1.60	m ² /E
Vertical flow constructed wetland (VFCW)		
Area	2,000.00	m ²
Depth	0.60	m
Volume	1,200	m ³
Width	17.67	m
Length	113.16	m
Porosity	0.35	-
Hydraulic volume	420	m ³
HRT	20.16	h
Horizontal flow constructed wetland (HFCW)		
Area	2,666.67	m ²
Depth	0.60	m
Volume	1,600	m ³
Width	29.71	m
Length	89.74	m
Porosity	0.35	-
Hydraulic volume	560	m ³
HRT	26.88	h
Total system		

Total hydraulic volume	980	m ³
Total area	4,667	m ²

Table A 13: System characteristics and dimensions for CS6 in the sensitivity analysis

Parameter	Value	Unit
Flow rate	500	m ³ /d
Settling tank volume	100	m ³
HRT (settling tank)	4.8	h
Vertical flow constructed wetland (VFCW)		
Area	430	m ²
Depth	0.6	m
Width	8.2	m
Length	52.5	m
Porosity	0.35	-
Hydraulic volume	90.3	m ³
HRT	4.3	h
Horizontal flow constructed wetland (HFCW)		
Area	670	m ²
Depth	0.6	m
Width	14.9	m
Length	45	m
Porosity	0.35	-
Hydraulic volume	140.7	m ³
HRT	6.8	h
Total system		
Total area	1100	m ²

Appendix B: Goal and scope

B 1. Assumptions

B 2. System boundaries

Appendix B 1. Assumptions

Table B 1: Standard transport distances (FRISCHKNECHT et al., 2007)

Material / Waste Management Facility	Transport Distance (km)
Gravel / Sand	50
Concrete	100
Metals	100
Plastics	100
Chemicals	100
Landfill facility	10

Table B 2: Estimations for electrical wiring in the storage tank

Component	Assumption
Cable channel	$3 \times (\text{Length} + \text{Width}) + 2 \times 3 \times \text{Height}$
Lighting	$1 \times \text{Width}$
Cable tray	$20 \times \text{Width}$
Main wiring to PLC/control panel	4 Width

Notes:

Estimations based on the drawings provided by FHNW for the storage tank at the WWTP Birs

Table B 3: Pipe length estimations for the storage tank systems

Component	Size	Assumption
Groundwater from GW lowering shafts	DN200	$1/3 \times \text{Length}$
Service water	DN80	$\text{Length} + \text{Width}$
	DN200	$2 \times \text{Height}$
Water inlet	DN300	$1/3 \times \text{Length}$
Cable channel	DN100	$3 \times (\text{Length} + \text{Width})$
Overflow	DN300	$1 \times \text{Width} + 1 \times \text{Width}$
Discharge line (heat connection)	DN200	$1 \times \text{Width} + 2 \times \text{Height}$
Filling rinse chamber (WAR)	DN100	$1 \times \text{Width}$
Mixed water pump drainage	DN300	$1 \times \text{Width} + 2 \times \text{Height} + \text{Length}$

Notes:

Estimations based on the drawings provided by FHNW for the storage tank at the WWTP Birs
DN refers to the nominal diameter of the pipe. The material used is polyethylene.

Appendix B 2. System boundaries

Figure B 1: System boundary for the operation phase of the WWTP

Figure B 2: System boundary for the construction phase of the storage tank and WWTP operation

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Figure B 3: System boundary for the operation phase of the storage tank and WWTP operation

Figure B 4: System boundary for the construction phase of the RSF “as built”

Figure B 5: System boundary for the operation phase of the RSF “as built”

Figure B 6: System boundary for the construction phase of the improved constructed wetland

Figure B 7: System boundary for the construction phase of the Filtration-Adsorption system

Figure B 8: System boundary for the construction phase of the gravel and sand filter

Figure B 9: System boundary for the construction phase of URS filter

Figure B 10: System boundary for the construction phase of the BRC

Appendix C: Life Cycle Inventory data

C 1. LCI for the construction and operation phase

C 2. Water quality

C 3. Ecoinvent flows

C 4. LCI of auxiliary processes

Appendix C 1. LCI for the construction and operation phase

Table C 1: Life cycle inventory for the construction of CS1

Parameter	CS1c	CS1d	CS1e	CS1f
Excavation and earthworks				
Excavation Volume (m ³)	50,630.41	66,375	40,621.63	49,414.06
Structural materials				
Concrete (m ³)	5,517.80	3,417	3,879.19	3,417
Reinforcing steel (Mg)	878.34	693	798.11	693
Reinforced concrete channel DN3000 (m)	-	18	18	18
Reinforced concrete channel DN800 (m)	-	110	110	110
Plastic components				
PE-HD DN80 (m)	170	-	-	-
PE-HD DN100 (m)	620	-	-	-
PE-HD DN150 (m)	-	3,060	1,530	1,530
PE-HD DN200 (m)	157.27	-	-	-
PE-HD DN250 (m)	-	1,615	807.50	807.50
PE-HD DN300 (m)	313.64	1,790	895	895
Geotextile (m ²)	-	59,400	29,700	29,700
Pond liner (m ²)	-	19,650	5,207.22	8,835.48
HDPE tank (kg)	-	-	770,00	770,00
Natural and composite materials				
Calciumcarbonate 2/5 (m ³)	-	2,760	375	375
Sand 0/2 (m ³)	-	8,040	5,025	5,025
Gravel 2/8 (m ³)	-	9,250	4,625	4,625
Reeds (pcs)	-	128,300	64,150	64,150
Metal materials				
Stainless steel (Mg)	3.30	7.30	4.50	4.50
Galvanized steel (Mg)	0.25	34	17	17
Electrical and control systems				
Electronics (kg)	22	-	-	-
Wiring (Mg)	1.16	7.64	3.82	3.82
Stainless steel (Mg)	0.37	3.23	1.62	1.62
Mechanical components				
Pump 25 l/s (pcs)	10	2	2	2
Pump 3.75 l/s (pcs)	-	-	1	1

Stirrer (pcs)	-	-	1	1
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Table C 2: Life-Cycle Inventory for the operation phase of CS1

Parameter	CS1b	CS1c	CS1d	CS1e	CS1f
Operational Inputs					
Biofloculant solution (m ³)	-	-	-	6,750	6,750
Replacement components					
Pump 25 l/s (pcs)	-	10	2	2	2
Pump 3.75 l/s (pcs)	-	-	-	1	1
Stirrer (pcs)	-	-	-	1	1
Energy consumption					
Pump 25 l/s (MWh)	-	384.60	25.67	22.06	22.06
Pump 3.75 l/s (MWh)	-	-	-	0.02	0.02
Stirrer (MWh)	-	-	-	5.36	5.36
WWPT energy demand (MWh)	7,351.31	7,351.31	-	-	-

Table C 3: Life cycle inventory for the construction of CS3

Parameter	CS3c
Excavation and earthworks	
Excavation volume (m ³)	36,488.16
Structural materials	
Concrete (m ³)	4,006.40
Reinforcing steel (Mg)	637.75
Plastic materials	
PE-HD DN80 (m)	139.20
PE-HD DN100 (m)	496.80
PE-HD DN200 (m)	126.47
PE-HD DN300 (m)	252.04
Metal materials	
Stainless steel (Mg)	2.87
Galvanized steel (Mg)	0.18
Electrical and control systems	
Electronics (kg)	22.00
Stainless steel (Mg)	0.30
Wiring (kg)	798.04
Mechanical components	

Pump (25 l/s)	7.00
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Table C 4: Life cycle inventory for the operation of CS3

Parameter	CS3b	CS3c
Operational inputs		
Flocculant (Mg)	205.81	205.81
Replacement components		
Pump 25 l/s (pcs)	-	7.00
Energy consumption		
Electronics (MWh)	-	4.50
Pump 25 l/s (MWh)	-	373.54
WWPT energy demand (MWh)	7,139.93	7,139.93

Table C 5: Life cycle inventory for the construction of CS6

Parameter	CS6c	CS6d
Excavation and earthworks		
Excavation Volume (m ³)	661.85	3,141.30
Structural materials		
Concrete (m ³)	158.61	90.43
Reinforcing steel (Mg)	25.25	14.43
Natural and composite materials		
Reeds (pcs)	-	46,666.67
Gravel 2/8 (m ³)	-	2,800.00
Plastic components		
PE-HD DN80 (m)	22.36	-
PE-HD DN100 (m)	74.54	-
PE-HD DN200 (m)	30.42	-
PE-HD DN250 (m)	-	40.00
PE-HD DN300 (m)	36.33	-
PVC pipe DN100 (m)	-	1,639.08
Geotextile (m ²)	-	4,666.67
Pond liner (m ²)	-	4,666.67
Metal materials		
Cast iron (Mg)	-	0.06
Stainless steel (Mg)	0.79	0.0137
Galvanized steel (kg)	17.14	-
Electrical and control systems		
Electronics (kg)	22.00	21.00
Wiring (kg)	70.11	28.00
Stainless steel (kg)	43.31	43.13
Mechanical components		

Pump (25 l/s)	1.00	-
Pump (7 l/s) (pcs)	-	1.00

Table C 6: Life cycle inventory for the operation of CS6

Parameter	CS6b	CS6c	CS6d
Replacement components			
Pump (25 l/s) (pcs)	-	1.00	-
Pump (7 l/s) (pcs)	-	-	1.00
Operational inputs			
Flocculant (Mg)	3.77	3.77	-
Energy consumption			
Electronics (kWh)	-	576.00	1658.88
Vegetation management (kWh)	-	-	420.03
Pump 25 l/s (MWh)	-	4.51	-
Pump 7 l/s (MWh)	-	-	2.01
WWPT energy demand (MWh)	130.69	130.69	-
Waste management			
Biowaste (Mg)	-	-	54.60

Table C 7: Life cycle inventory for the construction of CS2

Parameter	CS2c	CS2d	CS2e
Excavation and earthworks			
Excavation volume (m ³)	604.99	135.11	135.11
Structural materials			
Concrete (m ³)	134.25	40.92	40.92
Reinforcing steel (Mg)	21.37	5.84	5.84
Plastic components			
PE-HD DN50 (m)	-	80.00	80.00
PE-HD DN80 (m)	21.63	-	-
PE-HD DN100 (m)	72.11	-	-
PE-HD DN200 (m)	30.02	-	-
PE-HD DN250 (m)	-	55.50	55.50
PE-HD DN300 (m)	42.65	15.00	15.00
Filter housing (PVC-U) (Mg)	-	0.40	0.40
Silicon (kg)	-	53.00	53.00
Bags 25 & 1 microns (kg)	-	4.1	4.1
Natural and composite materials			
MS13X commercial zeolite (kg)	-	47,206.00	47,206.00
Sorbacid 911 commercial hydrotalcite (kg)	-	21,840.00	21,840.00
Sodium chloride (Mg)	-	48.68	48.68
Sodium carbonate (Mg)	-	132.27	132.27
Water (m ³)	-	2,006.22	2006.22
Metal materials			
Stainless steel (Mg)	0.73	24.52	24.58
Galvanized steel (Mg)	0,017	-	-
Electrical and control systems			
Electronics (kg)	22.00	35.75	35.75
Wiring (kg)	95.27	68.48	68.48
Stainless steel (kg)	41.90	40.95	40.95
Mechanical components			
Valves DN250 (pcs)	-	11.45	11.45
Valves DN300 (pcs)	-	2	2
Pump 130 l/s (pcs)	-	1	1
Pump 104 l/s (pcs)	-	1	1
Pump 47 l/s (pcs)	-	0.05	0.05
Pump 26 l/s (pcs)	-	0.05	0.05
Pump 25 l/s (pcs)	1	-	-

Stirrer (pcs)	-	1	1
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Table C 8: Life cycle inventory for the operation of CS2

Parameter	CS2b	CS2c	CS2d	CS2e
Operational inputs				
Bag 25 microns (kg)	-	-	981.95	981.95
Bag 1 microns (kg)	-	-	981.95	981.95
Sodium chloride (Mg)	-	-	212.61	1,849.95
Sodium carbonate (Mg)	-	-	403.76	4,497.32
Water (m ³)	-	-	5,985.26	71,454.91
Flocculant (Mg)	11.75	11.75	-	-
Replacement components				
Pump 130 l/s (pcs)	-	-	1.00	1.00
Pump 104 l/s (pcs)	-	-	1.00	1.00
Pump 47 l/s (pcs)	-	-	1.00	1.00
Pump 26 l/s (pcs)	-	-	1.00	1.00
Pump 25 l/s (pcs)	-	1.00	-	-
Stirrer	-	-	1.00	1.00
Energy consumption				
Electronics (kWh)	-	0.54	0.10	0.10
Valves (kWh)	-	-	0.75	0.75
Pump 130 l/s (MWh)	-	-	45.12	45.12
Pump 104 l/s (MWh)	-	-	24.76	24.76
Pump 47 l/s (MWh)	-	-	0.75	0.75
Pump 26 l/s (MWh)	-	-	0.57	0.57
Pump 25 l/s (MWh)	-	4.22	-	-
Stirrer (MWh)	-	-	0.23	0.23
WWPT energy demand (MWh)	122.33	122.33	-	-
Waste management				
Bag 25 microns (kg)	-	-	984.00	984.00
Bag 1 microns (kg)	-	-	984.00	984.00

Table C 9: Life cycle inventory for the construction of CS4a

Parameter	CS4a
Excavation and earthworks	
Excavation volume (m ³)	351.55
Structural materials	
Concrete (m ³)	4.47
Reinforcing steel (Mg)	0.38
Cast iron (Mg)	0.036
Plastic components	
PE-HD DN400 (m)	19.00
PVC pipe DN150 (m)	2.00
Geotextile (m ²)	87.10
Pond liner (m ²)	138.09
Natural and composite materials	
Bentonite mat (m ²)	535.00
Sand (m ³)	50.00
Gravel (m ³)	46.18

Table C 10: Life cycle inventory for the operation of CS4a

Parameter	CS4a
Energy consumption	
Machine operation (kWh)	37.91
Replacement components	
Sand (m ³)	50.00
Waste management	
Plant debris (kg)	10,767.74
Sand (m ³)	50.00

Table C 11: Life cycle inventory for the construction of CS4b

Parameter	CS4b
Excavation and earthworks	
Excavation Volume (m ³)	356.49
Structural materials	
Concrete (m ³)	5.22
Reinforcing steel (Mg)	0.83
Plastic components	
PE-HD DN90 (m)	51.69
PE-HD DN200 (m)	117.37
PVC pipe DN150 (m)	2.00
PVC pipe DN200 (m)	2.00
PVC pipe DN400 (m)	5.00
Geotextile (m ²)	182.80
Natural and Composite Materials	
AA shell & minerals (m ³)	273.71
Metal materials	
Cast iron (Mg)	0.065
Stainless steel (Mg)	0.006

Table C 12: Life cycle inventory for the construction of CS5

Parameter	CS5
Excavation and earthworks	
Excavation volume (m ³)	322.37
Plastic components	
PE-HD DN160 (m)	30.00
Geotextile (m ²)	262.99
PVC pipe DN150 (m)	2.00
Natural and composite materials	
Plants (pcs)	1,024.03
Mulch (kg)	1,459.24
Soil (m ³)	153.60
Gravel (m ³)	102.40

Table C 13: Life cycle inventory for the operation of CS5

Parameter	CS5
Replacement components	
Mulch (kg)	583.70
Energy consumption	
Machine operation (kWh)	47.34
Waste management	
Plant debris (kg)	7,680.22
Mulch (kg)	1,459.24

Table C 14: Life cycle inventory for the construction of CS0

Parameter	CS0c
Excavation and earthworks	
Excavation volume (m ³)	259.07
Structural materials	
Concrete (m ³)	98.66
Reinforcing steel (Mg)	15.71
Plastic Components	
PE-HD DN100 (m)	60.24
PE-HD DN200 (m)	14.19
PE-HD DN300 (m)	32.77
Metal materials	
Cast iron (Mg)	64.60
Stainless steel (Mg)	0.011
Galvanized steel (Mg)	0.010
Electrical and control systems	
Electronics (kg)	21.00
Wiring (kg)	64.13
Stainless steel (kg)	34.58
Mechanical components	
Pump (25 l/s)	1

Table C 15: Life cycle inventory for the operation of CS0

Parameter	CS0b	CS0c
Operational Inputs		
Pump (25 l/s)	-	1
Flocculant (Mg)	0.15	0.15
Energy Consumption		
Pump 25 l/s (MWh)	-	0.50
WWPT energy demand (MWh)	25.88	25.88
Electronics (MWh)	-	0.11

Appendix C 2. Water quality inputs

Table C 16: Influent and effluent water quality parameters and removal efficiencies for CSO treatment technologies

Parameter		CS1	CS2	CS3	CS6
	Water flow m ³	27,000,000	449,280	26,223,630	480,000
TSS	Inflow (mg/L)	150	418	150	150
	Outflow (mg/L)	7.5	20.9	7.5	3.8
	Elimination (%)	95	95	95	97.5
COD	Inflow (mg/L)	200	560	200	200
	Outflow (mg/L)	42	173.6	20	30
	Elimination (%)	79	69	90	85
TN	Inflow (mg/L)	10	40	10	10
	Outflow (mg/L)	4	16	2	3
	Elimination (%)	60	60	80	70
TP	Inflow (mg/L)	1.5	5	1.5	1.5
	Outflow (mg/L)	0.3	0.6	0.2	0.4
	Elimination (%)	80	89	90	75
Cr	Inflow (µg/L)	6.5	24.5	6.5	6.5
	Outflow (µg/L)	1.8	7.4	0.3	3.3
	Elimination (%)	72	70	95	50
Cu	Inflow (µg/L)	60	973	60	60
	Outflow (µg/L)	13	48.7	3	30
	Elimination (%)	78	95	95	50
Zn	Inflow (µg/L)	200	3730	200	200
	Outflow (µg/L)	60	373	20	100
	Elimination (%)	70	90	90	50
Cd	Inflow (µg/L)	0.7	2.5	0.7	0.7
	Outflow (µg/L)	0.2	0.8	0.04	0.4
	Elimination (%)	75	70	95	50
Pb	Inflow (µg/L)	13	43	13	13
	Outflow (µg/L)	4.7	12.9	0.1	6.5
	Elimination (%)	64	70	99	50
Ni	Inflow (µg/L)	6	231	6	6
	Outflow (µg/L)	1.4	46.2	2.1	3
	Elimination (%)	77	80	65	50

Notes: The water flow refers to the 30-year lifetime of the systems.

The removal efficiencies for CS3 were determined based on typical influent concentrations in wastewater treatment plants and corresponding effluent values reported in the literature. For COD, TN, and TP, values were obtained from DWA (2021), while for heavy metals from VRIENS et al. (2017), and for TSS from BROMBACH et al. (2005).

Table C 17: Influent and effluent water quality parameters and removal efficiencies for urban runoff treatment technologies

Parameter		CS4a	CS4b	CS5
TSS	Inflow (mg/L)	200.0	200.0	200.0
	Outflow (mg/L)	20.0	14.0	44.0
	Elimination (%)	90.0	93	78
COD	Inflow (mg/L)	100.0	100.0	100.0
	Outflow (mg/L)	33.0	32.0	50.0
	Elimination (%)	67.0	68	50
TN	Inflow (mg/L)	3.0	3.0	3.0
	Outflow (mg/L)	1.5	0.8	2.1
	Elimination (%)	49	73	30
TP	Inflow (mg/L)	0.3	0.3	0.3
	Outflow (mg/L)	0.2	0.1	0.2
	Elimination (%)	30.0	55	30
Cr	Inflow (µg/L)	40.0	40.0	40.0
	Outflow (µg/L)	20.0	16.8	4.0
	Elimination (%)	50.0	58	90
Cu	Inflow (µg/L)	60.0	60.0	60.0
	Outflow (µg/L)	60.0	12.0	13.8
	Elimination (%)	0.0	80	77
Zn	Inflow (µg/L)	180.0	180.0	180.0
	Outflow (µg/L)	50.4	46.8	19.8
	Elimination (%)	72.0	74	89
Cd	Inflow (µg/L)	5.0	5.0	5.0
	Outflow (µg/L)	2.0	0.4	1.0
	Elimination (%)	60.0	92	80
Pb	Inflow (µg/L)	20.0	20.0	20.0
	Outflow (µg/L)	5.0	3.8	3.6
	Elimination (%)	75.0	81	82
Ni	Inflow (µg/L)	19.0	19.0	19.0
	Outflow (µg/L)	10.1	19.0	3.4
	Elimination (%)	47.0	0	82

Notes: The total water flow over the 30-year lifespan is 95,040 m³.

Appendix C 3. Ecoinvent flows

Table C 18: Ecoinvent flows for the construction phase (I)

Parameter	Database entry	Source location	Conversion factor	Distance (km)
Excavation and Earthworks				
Excavation Volume (m ³)	Excavation, hydraulic digger	RER	1,600	50
Structural Materials				
Concrete (m ³)	concrete production, 35MPa, for building construction, with cement, CEM II/A	GLO	2,240	50
Reinforcing Steel (Mg)	Reinforcing steel production	Europe without Austria	-	100
Reinforced Concrete pipe (m)	See Table C 23		-	100
Plastic Components				
PE-HD DN50 (m)	Polyethylene pipe, DN 200, SDR 41	RER	0.64	100
PE-HD DN80 (m)	Polyethylene pipe, DN 200, SDR 41	RER	1.86	100
PE-HD DN100 (m)	Polyethylene pipe, DN 200, SDR 41	RER	2.7	100
PE-HD DN150 (m)	Polyethylene pipe, DN 200, SDR 41	RER	5.68	100
PE-HD DN200 (m)	Polyethylene pipe, DN 200, SDR 41	RER	9.04	100
PE-HD DN250 (m)	Polyethylene pipe, DN 200, SDR 41	RER	13.52	100
PE-HD DN300 (m)	Polyethylene pipe, DN 200, SDR 41	RER	20.68	100
PVC pipe DN100 (m)	See Table C 24		1.16	100
PVC pipe DN150 (m)	See Table C 24		2.78	100
PVC pipe DN200 (m)	See Table C 24		4.43	100
PVC pipe DN400 (m)	See Table C 24		18.51	100
Geotextile (m ²)	Polypropylene, granulate	RER	0.4	100
Pond liner (m ²)	Polyethylene pipe, DN 200, SDR 41	RER	0.64	100
HDPE tank (kg)	Polyethylene, high density, granulate	RER	-	400
Filter housing (PVC-U) (Mg)	See Table C 24		-	100
Bag 25 & 1 microns (kg)	textile production, nonwoven polypropylene, spunbond	RoW	-	400
Natural and Composite Materials				
Calciumcarbonate 2/5 (m ³)	Limestone, crushed, washed	CH	2,711	50

Sand 0/2 (m ³)	Gravel and sand quarry operation	CH	1,600	50
Gravel 2/8 (m ³)	Gravel production, crushed	CH	1,680	50

Table C 19: Ecoinvent flows for the construction phase (II)

Parameter	Database entry	Source location	Conversion factor	Distance (km)
MS13X commercial zeolite (kg)	See Table C 25		-	300
Sorbacid 911 commercial hydrotalcite (kg)	See Table C 26		-	600
Sodium chloride (Mg)	sodium chloride, powder	RER	-	50
Sodium carbonate (Mg)	Soda production, solvay process sodium bicarbonate	RoW	-	50
Bentonite mat (m ²)	See Table C 27		-	200
AA shells and minerals	Self-conducted LCA		-	100
Mulch (kg)	bark chips production, hardwood, at sawmill	Europe without Switzerland	-	50
Metal materials				
Stainless Steel (Mg)	steel production, chromium steel 18/8, hot rolled	RER	-	100
Galvanized steel (Mg)	See Table C 28		-	-
Cast iron (Mg)	Cast iron production	RER	-	100
Electrical and Control Systems				
Electronics (kg)	Electronics, for control units	RER	-	100
Wiring (Mg)	Cable, unspecified	GLO	-	20
Mechanical Components				
Pump 130 l/s (pcs)	Water pump production, 22kW	GLO	0.833	200
Pump 104 l/s (pcs)	Water pump production, 22kW	GLO	0.833	200
Pump 47 l/s (pcs)	Water pump production, 22kW	GLO	0.367	200
Pump 25 l/s (pcs)	Water pump production, 22kW	GLO	0.367	200
Pump 3.75 l/s (pcs)	Water pump production, 22kW	GLO	0.0367	200
Stirrer	See Table C 29		-	200
Valves DN250 (pcs)	See Table C 30		-	100

Notes: For all material flows, transportation was modelled using "transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO3." An additional transportation mode applies to MS13X commercial zeolite, which is shipped from China by sea over a distance of 18,350 km. The corresponding ecoinvent flow used for this process is "transport, freight, sea, container ship."

Table C 20: Ecoinvent flows for the operation phase

Parameter	Database entry	Source location	Conversion factor	Distance (km)
Operational Inputs				
Biofloculant solution (m ³)	See Table C 31		-	580
Floculant (Mg)	market for iron(III) chloride, without water, in 40% solution state	GLO	-	50
Energy Consumption				
Electricity mix	market group for electricity, medium voltage	RER	-	-
Waste Management				
Bag 25 & 1 microns (kg)	treatment of waste plastic, mixture, municipal incineration	GLO	-	15
Sand (m ³)	inert material landfill construction	RER	1,600	15

Table C 21: OpenLCA elementary flows for water quality inventory

Pollutant	OpenLCA elementary flow
TSS	Suspended solids, unspecified
COD	COD, Chemical Oxygen Demand
N _{tot}	Nitrogen
P _{tot}	Phosphorus
Cr	Chromium III
Cu	Copper ion
Zn	Zinc II
Cd	Cadmium II
Pb	Lead II
Ni	Nickel II

Notes:

The flows listed correspond to the category "Elementary flows/Emission to water/unspecified" within the ecoinvent database.

Appendix C 4: Life Cycle Inventory of auxiliar processes

Table C 22: Inventory data for reinforced concrete

Component	Value	Unit	Flow
Reinforced concrete	1	m ³	
Concrete	0.98	m ³	concrete, 50MPa
Density of concrete	2,240	kg/m ³	
Steel (reinforcement)	0.02	m ³	reinforcing steel
Density of steel	7,800	kg/m ³	

Notes:

According to UGOCHUKWU et al. (2020) , the weight of steel reinforcement per cubic meter of concrete typically ranges between 110 and 150 kg/m³ for retaining walls. This accounts for approximately 2% of the total weight of a reinforced concrete structure.

Table C 23: Inventory data for reinforced concrete pipes

Parameter	Value	Unit	Flow
Reinforced Concrete pipes	1	kg	
Concrete	922	g	Concrete, 50MPa (1 m ³ ; 2240 kg/ m ³)
Reinforced Steel	78	g	Reinforcing steel (1 kg)

Notes:

The composition were derived from the Environmental Product Declaration for reinforced concrete pipe (EPD AUSTRALASIA, 2023). It was assumed that components such as cement, aggregates, admixtures, fly ash, silica fume, and water are part of the production of concrete. Therefore, instead of integrating each component into the present inventory, only the process concrete was considered as the sum of these components.

The concrete flow is taken from the "Concrete, 50MPa" flow in OpenLCA, with a functional unit of 1 m³

The reinforced steel flow is directly taken from the " Reinforcing steel " flow in OpenLCA, with a functional unit of 1 kg.

Table C 24: Inventory data for 1 kg of Polyvinylchloride

Parameter	Value	Unit	Flow
Polyvinylchlorid granules	1	kg	market for polyvinylchloride, suspension polymerised - GLO
Extrusion	1	kg	market for extrusion, plastic pipes - GLO

Table C 25: Inventory data for 1 ton zeolite

Parameter	Value	Unit	Flow
Bauxite	609	kg	market for bauxite-
Sand	373	kg	market for sand
Rock sand	177	kg	market for salt
Limestone	32	kg	market for limestone, crushed, washed
Intermediates for zeolite filter cake + silicate prod.			
Water for steam production	1.2	m ³	market for water, deionised
Compressed air	51.8	Nm ³	market for compressed air, 700 kPa gauge
Cleaning agent	1.4	kg	Generic detergent-disinfectant, at plant
Stabilizers (tensides)	24.4	kg	market for non-ionic surfactant
Energy flow (Delivered energy)			
Electricity	6,830	MJ	market group for electricity, medium voltage
Coal	407	MJ	electricity production, hard coal
Oil heavy	3,649	MJ	heavy fuel oil, burned in refinery furnace
Oil average/light	599	MJ	Light fuel oil, burned in furnace 1MW of greenhouse
Diesel oil	474	MJ	diesel, burned in diesel-electric generating set, 10MW
Gas	9,135	MJ	electricity production, natural gas, conventional power plant
Recyclable materials			
Alu-residues	2.5	kg	aluminium scrap, post-consumer
NaOH (ca.15%-aq.)	69.9	kg	neutralising agent, sodium hydroxide-equivalent
Solid waste			
Mineral waste	36.1	kg	treatment of limestone residue, inert material landfill
Red-mud from bauxite mining	165.5	kg	treatment of redmud from bauxite digestion, residual material landfill
Inert chemicals	8.3	kg	treatment of residues, MSWI-WWT-SLF, inert waste, residual material landfill
Stags and ash	4.1	kg	treatment of fly ash and scrubber sludge, hazardous waste incineration
Regulated chemicals	8.8	kg	treatment of spent solvent mixture, hazardous waste incineration
Water consumption			
Process water	1.8	m ³	market for water, deionised
Cooling water	11.3	m ³	Water, cooling, unspecified natural origin
Washing water	2.2	m ³	market for tap water

Notes:

Proxy for the production of MS13X zeolite gathered from FAWER et al. (1998).

Table C 26: Inventory data for 1 kg Sorbacid 911

Parameter	value	unit	Flow
Magnesium oxide	0.5	kg	market for magnesium oxide
Aluminium hydroxide	0.3	kg	market for aluminium hydroxide
Sodium hydroxide	0.2	kg	market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state
Electricity	15	MJ	electricity, medium voltage, European attribute mix

Table C 27: Data inventory for 1 m² Bentonite mats

Material	Specific weight (kg/m ²)	Flow
PE Membrane	1.9	polyethylene, high density, granulate
PP Woven Geotextile	0.4	polypropylene, granulate
Bentonite Granules	16.5	Bentonite quarry operation
PP Non-woven Fabric	0.03	Textile production, nonwoven polypropylene, spunbond

Notes:
Specifications based on BECO BERMÜLLER (13.01.2025).

Table C 28: Inventory data for galvanized steel

Material	Value	Unit	Flow
Galvanized Steel	1	kg	-
Steel	980	g	Steel, low-alloyed, hot-rolled – RER (1 kg/unit)
Zinc	20	g	Zinc Coating, Coils - RER (1 m ² /unit)
Zinc Coating Area	0.00128	m ²	Calculated for 20 g of zinc
Coating Thickness	0.000042	m	-
Mean surface area	64	m ² /t	-

Notes:
The proportions of galvanized steel composition were derived from the Environmental Product Declaration for galvanized steel (EPD INTERNATIONAL, 2023).
The steel flow is directly taken from the "Steel, low-alloyed, hot-rolled" flow in OpenLCA, with a functional unit of 1 kg.

The Zinc flow is modeled using "Zinc Coating, Coils" with a functional unit of 1 m²

Table C 29: Inventory data for the stirrer production

Material	Value	Unit	Flow
Stainless steel	19	kg	steel production, chromium steel 18/8, hot rolled
Rubber	5	kg	silicone product production

Notes:

The proportions were derived from the inventory established by FARD and BARKDOLL (2021)

Table C 30: Inventory data for valves DN250 and DN300

Material	DN250	DN300	Flow
Fiber reinforced polyamide (kg)	4.5	6.4	glass fibre reinforced plastic production, polyamide, injection moulded
Ferrous metals (kg)	3.2	4.7	casting, steel, lost-wax
Other plastics and rubbers	0.9	1.4	market for synthetic rubber

Notes:

The proportions of the valves composition were derived from the Environmental Product Declaration for butterfly valve 565 (EPD INTERNATIONAL AB, 2022)

Table C 31: Inventory data for the preparation of 2% chitosan solution

Parameter	Value	Unit	Flow
Chitosan solution	225,000	L	
Density of the solution	1	kg/L	
Total weight of solution	225,000	kg	
Acetic acid	9,000	kg	OpenLCA flow: Acetic acid, without water, in 98% solution state
Chitosan	4,500	kg	See Table C 32
Water	211,500	kg	OpenLCA flow: Market group for tap water

Notes:

The composition of the solution is 97% water, 2% chitosan, and 1% acetic acid for one year application.

The values referred to the total 30 years-lifetime of the compact RSF.

The impact factors for chitosan are based on the work conducted by RIOFRIO et al. (2021). See values in Table C 32.

Table C 32: Environmental Impact Assessment for 1 kg of chitosan

Impact categories	Impact factor	Unit
Global warming	43.50	kg CO ₂ eq
Terrestrial acidification	0.14	kg SO ₂ eq
Freshwater eutrophication	0.0049	kg P eq
Marine eutrophication	0.0023	kg N eq
Freshwater ecotoxicity	0.57	kg 1,4- DCB
Marine ecotoxicity	0.77	kg 1,4- DCB
Water consumption	34.04	m ³

Notes:

The impact factors presented in this table are based on the "Chitosan-50%" from the work of RIOFRIO et al. (2021). However, these values do not include the environmental impacts associated with NaOH production.

Table C 33: Inventory data for 1 kWh from renewable sources

Parameter	Value	Unit	Database flow
Electricity mix (renewable energy)	1	kWh	Electricity, high voltage, wind power, import from Germany, renewable energy products - CH
	1	kWh	Electricity voltage transformation from high to medium voltage, renewable energy products - CH

Appendix D: Life Cycle Impact Assessment

D 1. Impact categories

D 2. Impact assessment results

D 3. Relative contribution of materials and services

D 4. Sensitivity analysis of impact assessment results

D 1. Impact categories

Table D 1: Environmental considerations of selected impact categories for LCA.

Impact Category	Environmental Considerations
<p>Climate Change (Global Warming Potential - GWP) It quantifies the radiative forcing caused by different greenhouse gases, including CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O (ROSENBAUM et al., 2018) Expressed in CO₂-equivalents (kg CO₂eq).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Climate change is driven by anthropogenic activities such as material production, which contribute to radiative forcing, leading to global temperature changes. (NEUBAUER, 2021) - Increased atmospheric CO₂ leads to aquatic acidification, affecting ecosystems by lowering pH levels. (WALLACE et al., 2025)
<p>Acidification Potential (TAP - Terrestrial Acidification Potential) Evaluates the contribution of emissions to acid rain formation and acidification of ecosystems, expressed in SO₂-eq (kg SO₂eq). (ROSENBAUM et al., 2018)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acid rain affects ecosystems by lowering the pH of water bodies, reducing biodiversity. (WALLACE et al., 2025) - Acidification is particularly detrimental to fish populations, as many species cannot tolerate pH fluctuations. (WALLACE et al., 2025)
<p>Eutrophication Potential Assesses the impact of nutrient enrichment in aquatic ecosystems. (ROSENBAUM et al., 2018) FEP (Freshwater Eutrophication Potential) Expressed in kg P-eq. MEP (Marine Eutrophication Potential) Expressed in kg N-eq.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It leads to excessive algal growth, reducing light penetration, thus limiting photosynthesis in submerged aquatic plants. (AKINNAWO, 2023). - Algal decomposition depletes dissolved oxygen, causing loss of biodiversity. (ROSENBAUM et al., 2018) - In freshwater ecosystems, phosphorus is the primary limiting nutrient, while nitrogen plays this role in marine environments. (OWENS, 2001)
<p>Ecotoxicity Potential Evaluates the potential of toxic emissions to harm aquatic life, measured in kg 1,4-dichlorobenzene equivalents (kg 1,4-DCB eq). (OGINAH et al., 2023) FETP (Freshwater Ecotoxicity Potential) METP (Marine Ecotoxicity Potential)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Heavy metal contamination is a significant global issue, with approximately 40% of lakes and rivers polluted. (ZAMORA-LEDEZMA et al., 2021) - Metals accumulate in aquatic organisms, causing oxidative damage, endocrine disruption, and immune depression. (ZAMORA-LEDEZMA et al., 2021)
<p>Water Use (WCP - Water Consumption Potential) Measures the volume of water consumed in production and operational processes, expressed in cubic meters (m³). (ROSENBAUM et al., 2018)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The environmental impact of water use depends on geographic and temporal availability. (ROSENBAUM et al., 2018) - It is defined to evaluate the depletion of the water, in order to determine the sustainability or unsustainability of the sources used. (OWENS, 2001)

D 2. Impact assessment results

Table D 2: Life Cycle Impact Assessment per kilogram of TSS removed from CSO water in the mean concentration scenario

Case study Impact category	CS1d	CS1e	CS1f	CS3b	CS3c	CS6d
Climate change [kg CO ₂ -Eq/kg TSS]	1.36E+00	2.98E+00	2.90E+00	6.81E-01	1.81E+00	3.49E+00
Acidification [kg SO ₂ -Eq/kg TSS]	4.05E-03	8.68E-03	8.55E-03	2.40E-03	5.12E-03	9.79E-03
Freshwater eutrophication [kg P-Eq/kg TSS]	2.14E-03	2.31E-03	2.31E-03	1.11E-03	1.14E-03	2.63E-03
Marine eutrophication [kg N-Eq/kg TSS]	8.36E-03	8.44E-03	8.44E-03	4.18E-03	4.19E-03	6.14E-03
Freshwater ecotoxicity [kg 1.4-DCB-Eq/kg TSS]	1.10E-01	1.31E-01	1.30E-01	3.45E-02	3.82E-02	1.90E-01
Marine ecotoxicity [kg 1.4-DCB-Eq/kg TSS]	2.70E-01	3.09E-01	2.95E-01	5.14E-02	1.53E-01	4.26E-01
Water Use [m ³ /kg TSS]	8.80E-03	1.20E+00	1.20E+00	9.23E-03	1.49E-02	3.82E-02

Table D 3: Life Cycle Impact Assessment per kilogram of TSS removed from CSO water in the peak concentration scenario

Case study Impact category	CS2b	CS2c	CS2d	CS2e
Climate change [kg CO ₂ -Eq/kg TSS]	2.86E-01	1.04E+00	7.33E+00	3.93E+01
Acidification [kg SO ₂ -Eq/kg TSS]	1.04E-03	2.99E-03	5.43E-02	3.26E-01
Freshwater eutrophication [kg P-Eq/kg TSS]	1.28E-03	1.30E-03	1.84E-03	4.56E-03
Marine eutrophication [kg N-Eq/kg TSS]	5.99E-03	6.00E-03	1.23E-02	1.41E-02
Freshwater ecotoxicity [kg 1.4-DCB-Eq/kg TSS]	2.28E-01	2.31E-01	2.43E-01	2.96E-01
Ecotoxicity marine [kg 1.4-DCB-Eq]	3.19E-01	3.91E-01	4.79E-01	9.79E-01
Water Use [m ³ /kg TSS]	3.66E-03	7.59E-03	1.71E-01	1.33E+00

Table D 4: Life Cycle Impact Assessment per kilogram of TSS removed in the urban runoff management

Case study	CS0b	CS0c	CS4a	█	CS5
Impact category					
Climate change [kg CO ₂ -Eq/kg TSS]	4.92E-01	5.66E+00	1.09E+00	█	7.67E-01
Acidification [kg SO ₂ -Eq/kg TSS]	1.71E-03	1.49E-02	3.16E-03	█	2.29E-03
Freshwater eutrophication [kg P-Eq/kg TSS]	2.04E-04	3.44E-04	1.19E-03	█	1.35E-03
Marine eutrophication [kg N-Eq/kg TSS]	9.43E-04	1.01E-03	2.54E-03	█	4.00E-03
Freshwater ecotoxicity [kg 1.4-DCB-Eq/kg TSS]	2.55E-02	4.34E-02	1.28E-01	█	4.52E-02
Ecotoxicity marine [kg 1.4-DCB-Eq]	3.75E-02	5.50E-01	1.98E-01	█	7.93E-02
Water Use [m ³ /kg TSS]	6.83E-03	3.33E-02	6.50E-03	█	5.72E-03

D 3. Relative results

Figure D 1: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 1b

Note: See Table C 2

Figure D 2: Relative impact contribution in the construction phase of case study 1c

Note: See Table C 1

Figure D 3: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 1c

Note: See Table C 2

Figure D 4: Relative impact contribution in the construction phase of case study 1d

Note: See Table C 1

Figure D 5: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 1d

Note: See Table C 2

Figure D 6: Relative impact contribution in the construction phase of case study 1e

Note: See Table C 1

Figure D 7: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 1e

Note: See Table C 2

Figure D 8: Relative impact contribution in the construction phase of case study 1f

Note: See Table C 1

Figure D 9: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 1f

Note: See Table C 2

Figure D 10: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 2b

Note: See Table C 8

Figure D 11: Relative impact contribution in the construction phase of case study 2c

Note: See Table C 7

Figure D 12: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 2c

Note: See Table C 8

Figure D 13: Relative impact contribution in the construction phase of case study 2d

Note: See Table C 7

Figure D 14: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 2d

Note: See Table C 8

Figure D 15: Relative impact contribution in the construction phase of case study 2e

Note: See Table C 7

Figure D 16: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 2e

Note: See Table C 8

Figure D 17: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 3b

Note: See Table C 4

Figure D 18: Relative impact contribution in the construction phase of case study 3c

Note: See Table C 3

Figure D 19: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 3c

Note: See Table C 4

Figure D 20: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 0b

Note: See Table C 15

Figure D 21: Relative impact contribution in the construction phase of case study 0c

Note: See Table C 14

Figure D 22: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 0c

Note: See Table C 15

Figure D 23: Relative impact contribution in the construction phase of case study 4a

Note: See Table C 9

Figure D 24: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 4a

Note: See Table C 10

Figure D 25: Relative impact contribution in the construction phase of case study 4b

Note: See Table C 11

Figure D 26: Relative impact contribution in the construction phase of case study 5

Note: See Table C 12

Figure D 27: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 5

Note: See Table C 13

Figure D 28: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 6b

Note: See Table C 6

Figure D 29: Relative impact contribution in the construction phase of case study 6c

Note: See Table C 5

Figure D 30: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 6c

Note: See Table C 6

Figure D 31: Relative impact contribution in the construction phase of case study 6d

Note: See Table C 5

Figure D 32: Relative impact contribution in the operation phase of case study 6d

Note: See Table C 6

D 4. Sensitivity analysis of impact assessment results

Figure D 33: Results for sensitivity analysis in case study 1

Figure D 34: Results for sensitivity analysis in case study 3

Figure D 35: Results for sensitivity analysis in case study 6

Figure D 36: Results for sensitivity analysis in case study 2

Figure D 37: Results for sensitivity analysis in case studies 4a, 4b and 5